

Facultad de Humanidades y Educación
Escuela de Educación

**English Language Teaching in Chile
and the Perception of
English for Specific Purposes as an Alternative Program to
Improve Learning Results:
A Descriptive Study**

Seminario para optar al Título de

Profesor de Inglés

y al Grado Académico de:

Licenciado en Educación Básica y
Media

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**Santiago – Chile
2011**

DEDICATION

Alan: *The hard work presented in the present thesis and throughout the program is dedicated to my supportive and unconditional mother and to my true friends.*

David: *To my unconditional and loving family, pillar and main support.*

Gonzalo: *Dedicated to my parents, without them this would not have been possible; and to my son, the engine that keeps me moving everyday.*

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Our deepest appreciation to Miss Roxana Painemilla, whose encouragement, committed guidance, and friendship allowed our success; and to Miss Silvina Zapata for her support.

Finally, to each other for being there all along.

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ABSTRACT

For the last decade, the Chilean government has been making efforts to improve the mastery of English achieved through the teaching-learning process of the subject at both primary and high school levels. Regardless of the efforts deployed, the results are far from satisfactory and great emphasis is being placed on finding methodologies and means to overcome this drawback. In answer to this issue, it is the aim of the present research to determine whether the different elements that make up the high school system in Chile would allow the incorporation of English for Specific Purposes in the classroom. To gather the information required, an exhaustive literature review was made to assess the *status quo* of English Language Teaching (ELT) in Chile and to define the requirements for the implementation of an ESP syllabus. In addition, the affective factors shown by the stakeholders in relation to ESP were assessed. A survey was performed in 5 schools representative of the Chilean reality. Based on the economical, managerial, infrastructural, governmental, instructional, and affective aspects studied, it was possible to determine that the Chilean education has the necessary conditions to improve the levels of teaching and learning English through the implementation of English for Specific Purposes (ESP) programs as an alternative and experimental method.

Durante la última década, el Gobierno de Chile ha realizado esfuerzos para mejorar el manejo del inglés logrado a través del proceso de enseñanza de la asignatura tanto en educación básica como media. A pesar de los esfuerzos llevados a cabo, los resultados están lejos de ser satisfactorios, es por eso que se ha puesto gran énfasis en la búsqueda de nuevas metodologías y otros medios para solucionar esta problemática. Como solución a este obstáculo, el objetivo del presente trabajo es determinar si los distintos elementos que son parte de la educación media chilena permiten la incorporación a la enseñanza media el Inglés para Fines Específicos (ESP) en las aulas. Se realizó una revisión exhaustiva de literatura relacionada al tema para reunir la información requerida y evaluar el estado de la enseñanza del inglés (ELT) en el país, y definir los requerimientos para la implementación de programas ESP. Además se evaluó los factores afectivos manifestados por los agentes educativos en relación a los principios de ESP. Se realizó una encuesta a 5 colegios representativos de la realidad chilena. Mediante el estudio de los distintos factores: económicos, administrativos, de infraestructura, gubernamentales, docentes, y afectivos fue posible determinar que la educación chilena cumple con las condiciones necesarias para mejorar su nivel de la enseñanza-aprendizaje del idioma inglés a través de la implementación de programas de Inglés para Fines Específicos (ESP) como un método alternativo experimental.

1. CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1. Overview

As appraised by the general Chilean citizen as well as international authorities, education in Chile is far from being at its best moment. In fact, 29% (5 billion CLP) of the 2011 national social budget is allotted to education (Department of Treasury, 2010) in the hope for improvement. In regards to English Language Teaching (ELT), new plans to learn English are being conducted and more English institutes and “Bilingual” schools are seen along the country. Besides, the Education budget was raised by 7.6% and an important amount was dedicated to scholarships, new and more effective evaluation systems, and educational resources, in general, delivered to seek notable improvements; however, results are not being achieved.

Fig. 1: *Proyecto de Presupuesto 2011- Budget Proposal* (Dirección de Presupuesto, web)

In order to have a clear view of what the Chilean ELT reality is, in relation to other countries, it is necessary to take into consideration important international standards of measurements. For instance, in a table assembled by Wikipedia in which, through Censuses, the amount of English speakers per country is shown Chile does not appear within the first hundred (some sources that form the table are the U.S Census Bureau, South African Census in Brief, Russian Census, among others). The latter cannot be good news for Chile since 9 of the top 10 English-speaking and second-language countries are developed; this data clearly conveys that the speaking of English is linked to economic growth. Another study developed by one of the most important chains of English Teaching Institutions and research entity, English First, conducted in 42 countries, placed Chile in the 36th place (EF EPI Índice de Nivel de Inglés 5), labeling it as *Very Low Level*. As stated by the same study, higher levels of English are directly related to most economical rates. For example:

- Higher exports.
- Higher wages (30% to 50%)
- More developed countries.
- Higher income per capita.
- More possible foreign investors.

(EF EPI Índice de Nivel de Inglés 7)

In other words, and, as it is witnessed and experienced by most non-native English-speaking developed countries, the levels of English displayed by their population carry within an important economic boost, which at the same time increases the need of Chile to gain better results and raise the amount of English-speaking people for the country's benefit as well as for the individual. This same study states that "La globalización exige el aprendizaje del inglés" 'Globalization demands the learning of English' (EF EPI Índice de Nivel de Inglés 6).

Chile's effort to meet the requirements that will lead to it into becoming a country where English is widely spoken contrasts with the conditions that ELT (English Language Teaching) currently has, e.g. the amount of English teaching hours invested at schools, the number of course books requested for parents to purchase, and the budget in general used for teachers, technologies, English labs, Radios, CD players, among other types of implementations seem to be enough to achieve excellent results; nevertheless, the results are discouraging. All these conditions should build altogether a rather effective learning environment ensuring an efficient learning. According to a study conducted in Europe in 2008 by the Education Department of the European Union, the Eurydice, the optimum conditions that must be held to ensure good results when teaching a second language are the following:

- Average age to begin studying ESL is 8

- Average amount of hours weekly must be between 5 and 8

(Education Department of EU, PDF file)

Our education laws state that ESL teaching should start by 5th grade (students are around 10 years of age); however most schools have chosen to start implementing it earlier. Regarding teaching hours, most schools comply with the minimum set by the authorities, but many schools in Chile are already complying with the two minimum requirements recommended by the study above mentioned (Education Department of EU, PDF file) although the Ministry does not impose these requirements on these schools. In other words, Chile complies with the minimum required conditions that the study conducted by the European Union recommended, but the results do not match the situation.

Also, the results of a national exam (SIMCE, further explained ahead) taken in 2010 revealed that there are various factors that play an important role in the success of the students acquiring a second language, such as the age at which they start studying English, the amount of English-teaching hours, teachers who speak a high percentage of the class in English (and teachers who do not), and the students that take extra hours of English outside the school (Gobierno de Chile, *PowerPoint* file). Besides, according to an interview with Michelle Bachelet in 2004 in La Tercera newspaper, only 3 percent of the high school

graduated population uses the English taught at school, and only 2 percent of the Chilean population speaks it. Ironically, it seems an acceptable figure since, apparently, no significant need for English-speakers has been promoted and communicated through campaigns in the country. In addition, it seems as if the figures above tell us that the English taught during school years does not have a purposeful goal. Nonetheless, nowadays, Chile is considered to be an open economy and this might be the reason why many international enterprises such as Econergy and Barrick Gold Chile have established on Chilean soil. With these two different companies as examples, the importance for the future Chilean students to be taught purposeful English that can result in a useful tool to be used in the workplace may be inferred.

The latter information about the importance and at the same time deficient situation of English in Chile leads us to believe that a radical and necessary change must take place in the system. For instance, students sitting for the SIMCE exam had to reach a minimum of 134 points (75 percent TOEIC Bridge test level [Test of English for International Communication]) which would certify them as having the minimum level of English (explained ahead), the bad news is that only one out of ten students achieved this score which means that only 11 percent of students got certified; the average obtained by the total number of students who sat for the test in Chile being 55 percent TOEIC Bridge test level.

As a comparison, when the TOEIC Bridge test was conducted in Japan, it delivered a much encouraging average score: 119 points (66 percent of certification). Why did they achieve better results? What needs to be changed to achieve such results? What is the Chilean system lacking? What was truly answered through the results of this test that was designed to diagnose English Language Teaching is that modifications and improvements must be made, and in fact there are changes already being made, since such nationwide exam is the first of its kind to be applied in South America.

It is important to clarify that the SIMCE test is a version of TOEIC Bridge test. The Educational Testing Service (ETS) defines TOEIC Bridge test as a “starting point on the path to workplace success for English-language learners,” and it emphasizes the fact that as it is “designed for beginning learners, it measures the listening and reading comprehension skills used in an international environment” (Educational Testing Service, web). The SIMCE test is truly a powerful and very useful tool to know the Chilean ELT reality. Nevertheless, a diagnosis does only measure the status of an object of study.

This status quo gave birth to the main idea of the present study: to begin planning an eventual modification, improvement or change at any level, it is of utmost importance to firstly develop a complete and thorough study of the

factors that will determine the feasibility (whether it can be achieved) and plausibility (whether it is able to come true) of conducting changes that might make, in our case, EFL more effective in the teaching-learning relationship and more useful for the would-be speakers of English in our country. These factors are basically economic and investment, motivation, methodology, and the need for learning the language, among others. These and other aspects will be further analyzed in the present research work.

Another important aspect that must be considered is the current Chilean economic and cultural situation, which brings along the need for our country of having stronger connections with English-speaking countries, or countries with English as their “Lingua Franca,” due to its participation in various trade agreements with them. This has led, for instance, the Chilean Ministry of Education to create and implement special programs that enable students to travel and study a semester in a foreign country (e.g. English Opens Doors), alongside many other programs designed to enhance the learning of English in the country.

As shown in the literature, a number of alternatives or complements to these programs are being developed and implemented around the world, in the local arena, and following the world tendencies, there are efforts and research being

performed on the application of new methodologies such as the teaching of English through drama, as Lizasoain and Ortiz de Zárate elaborate in their publication “Efficiency and Effectiveness of Drama Techniques in the English Classroom”, as well as E-Tivities, which is an internet-based English learning system designed by Frank Miller, pedagogical researcher. The previously mentioned innovative English teaching systems are currently either at their initial study-process, and others, in their final stage of study throughout the world. It is also important to mention that in several countries, such as Chile, these mechanisms are being implemented mainly privately, tertiary, and in some technical schools.

In spite of the efforts aforementioned, and, as suggested by some international organizations (OEA, World Bank, UNICEF, and the OECD), the Chilean education system has many flaws and that its current state of affairs is insufficient and inefficient to meet teachers, students, staff, parents and others’ needs. The inadequacy mentioned previously has had its utmost manifestation in thousands of students participating in protest marches during the present year (2011), in the main cities of the country as well as hunger strikes on demand for free, more equal and better quality education. ELT, which is the scope of our interest, of course, is involved. Regardless of the results of the movements,

these activities highlight the needs that have to be satisfied; a change at some level is being demanded.

This research is based on the need for improvement manifested by our educational system, and it proposes that the incorporation of the tenets of ESP (English for Specific Purposes) may be a way to begin changing how and what is taught in high-schools: to start learning English following the basis and principles of such new methodology, which is believed to contribute to improving ELT in Chile, and which may be of interest and of great input to the students' future studies and work-related activities.

According to the authors of the present research study, the teaching methodologies being used in most schools of Chile are stale and do not nourish students' motivation, curiosity nor their desire to learn English; therefore, as established by Lizasoain and Ortiz (1) "English teaching methodology used in this country is neither efficient nor effective. Consequently, a different methodology is urgently needed," and they further propose that:

"Students do not have many opportunities to actively participate. In a typical English class, students are required to use their receptive skills far more than their productive skills, which lead students to be deficient in

writing and speaking skills. Furthermore, teachers tend to base their teaching on textbooks only, leaving little time to creative experiences.”

(Lizasoain and Ortiz 2)

Unfortunately, these textbook-based methodologies are engraved in the English teaching system and it can be seen throughout the wide range of schools in Chile, leaving only a selective group of schools which are the exception to the rule. The majority of these schools either belong to the upper classes or are selective high-demand schools. The last statement extrapolates us to the finding of a system that has the capability of erasing the negative encrypted message mentioned before about the status of our education in order to write a new story of good EFL results that will eventually aid the students in their future jobs, and enhance their general knowledge. Effectiveness, equality, accessibility, objectivity, and being straight-to-the-point are factors that *the system* must contain within its principles; and, it is believed by the authors of this project that ESP complies with what is needed.

1.2. Problem Statement

What the present investigation seeks is to determine, through thorough literature review and study, whether Chile and its educational regime have the necessary elements that allow a potential incorporation of an innovative English teaching

methodology into the high-school classrooms, and try to understand how the stakeholders of the learning-teaching process, specially the students, perceive the task of learning English and how the affective factors may influence the learning process.

The goal of the present thesis has a solid foundation of theoretical supported material which will identify and define the present object of study which is English for Specific Purposes. Moreover, this research will demonstrate literature regarding education in Chile and worldwide. In addition, this investigation will describe and analyze the stakeholders' perception of a different teaching and learning methodology. As researchers of this work, the main goal is focused on studying if the Chilean standard of education would possibly comply with a potential implementation of a new teaching and learning methodology; therefore, analyzing the stakeholders' perception is necessary to make a conclusion, and possibly, determine if English for Specific Purposes has the required elements to operate.

2. CHAPTER TWO: THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1. Key Concepts

2.1.1. ELT, EFL and ESL, and ESP and its Branches

In order to provide a clear definition of some of the concepts around which the present research will revolve, it is necessary to explain and clarify the existing

differences among English Language Teaching (ELT), English as a Foreign Language (EFL), English as a Second Language (ESL), and English for Specific Purposes (ESP) and the branches to which the latter is directly related.

Firstly, English Language Teaching (ELT) is instructing or imparting knowledge about a language, in this case, English, to people who have the desire to learn it. Language teaching is “teaching people to speak and understand a foreign language” (The Free Dictionary, web). In English Language Teaching there are branches in which there are different ways of approaching learning and teaching English. One of these is English as a Foreign Language (EFL), a method used to teach English in a place where English is not used for communicating within the community; however, the teacher has the mission to find and create English models for the students (Lee Gunderson, Web). On the other hand, English as a Second Language is considered an approach towards English in countries that are part of the *Outer Circle*. (Braj Kachru, web). The *Outer Circle* is defined by David Crystal as the countries in which English is not the dominant language. In addition, Anthony highlights Dudley-Evans’s “English for Specific Purposes (ESP) is the language defined to meet specific needs of the learners as well as the underlying methodology and activities in terms of the discipline it serves.” One of its main characteristics is the fact that it is centered on the six most

important patterns of all languages: grammar, lexis, register, study skills, discourse, and genre (Anthony, web)

English for Specific Purposes (ESP) is an important component of English Language Teaching; its main doctrine is to analyze the students' needs and prepare students for communicating properly in the area of their interest (Pedro Fuertes 11). This type of English language teaching and learning methodology was developed due to the world's demands for better-prepared professionals, but firstly it became more popular by the end of the Second World War due to economic expansion in the international context, during the post-war period when the United States of America became a dominant country in the world. All of these conditions led English teaching to become an important matter of education for it was considered a need (Hutchinson and Waters 6).

There are other definitions of ESP such as: "ESP courses are those where the syllabus and materials are determined in all essentials by the prior analysis of the communication needs of the learner," as defined by Munby (qtd. in Herbolich 154); or, "ESP is an approach to language teaching in which all decisions as to content and method are based on the learner's reason for learning" (Hutchinson and Waters 19).

In a few words, English for Specific Purposes is an approach towards the teaching of English, different from TESL and TEFL; however, it relies on principles and bases, which tenets are going to be developed below.

2.1.2. ESP and its Tenets

ESP has variables which give it a sense of flexibility and adaptability towards the different educational context, countries, and social groups in which it may be applied.

According to Dudley-Evans (15), the variables are:

1. ESP may be related to or designed for specific disciplines.
2. ESP may use, in specific teaching situations, a different methodology from that of General English.
3. ESP is likely to be designed for adult learners, either at a tertiary level institution or in a professional work situation.
4. ESP is generally designed for intermediate or advanced students.
5. Most ESP courses assume some basic knowledge of language systems.

In other words, ESP acts as a mouldable teaching methodology and as a flexible approach towards ELT that allows a wider range of interests and learning styles to be covered as point 1 suggests. ESP focuses on different areas or disciplines, giving the students the opportunity to choose a specific field of study or

specialization. ESP is, normally, considered an English program for adults, and is taught in universities and some institutes. Kristen Gatehouse goes further by suggesting that it could perfectly be for learners at a secondary school level (web). Besides, it has recently been implemented at secondary level in some countries, as in Italy. For instance, Italian expert Eugenio Cianflone, in *ESP in a secondary Italian school*, discusses the methods by which ESP can lead to successful learning, emphasizing Dudley-Evans's suggestion that "ESP features can be used in senior secondary school classes" (2). Cianflone also mentions the importance of teamwork that existed during the program development process, which consisted of three principal members who were the General English (GE) instructor, the social sciences teacher, and the ESP expert. Each of the members was assigned a specific and different task in the development of the program so as to ensure a successful identification of the students' needs (Cianflone 2). Cianflone mentions that an ESP group was exposed to a 2-year General English program in order to avoid language barriers (grammar explanations) and reach a homogenous level.

After implementing the ESP program, the learners were asked a set of questions in order to find out what their opinion was and how they felt about it. Students expressed their approval to this *new* kind of methodology and said that it had been an *interesting* experience, as Cianflone stated. In addition, attendance

increased as the students got more interested throughout the course. Cianflone suggests that “an ESP course can be designed for secondary school because young age has no effect on specialist learning,” and that despite each educational institution’s context, the aim is the same: “to prepare students for further education or for the world of work” (4).

Yet, so as to know how a new program might affect the students’ learning and their emotional aspects, it is necessary to further analyze the factors involved, which is done in the next item.

2.1.3. Affective Factors

2.1.3.1. The Affective Domain

Brown (135) defines the affective domain as the emotional side of human behavior in its relation to the cognitive area. The affective domain is composed of both personality factors and extrinsic factors. As proposed by Bloom (qtd. in Brown 153) a comprehensive definition of the affective domain classifies it in five levels: 1. Receiving is the essential and basic level of the domain. Individuals have to be conscious about the surroundings and environment and they have to be willing to receive the input the environment offers “to tolerate a stimulus, not avoid it- and give a stimulus their controlled or selected attention” (153); 2. Responding implies a subject’s commitment to the situation and it is related to a sense of achievement; 3. Valuing involves “learners’ placing worth on a thing, a

behavior or person” (153); 4. Organization is the arrangement of values that the individuals construct. Learners structure and categorize their values creating a system of beliefs; and 5. A values system implies the behaviors subjects have which reflect their internalized values, and integrated beliefs, ideas and attitudes towards the world they are related to.

This definition of Affective Domain is widely used in the area of language learning for it explains how the affective domain relates to the process of language learning. Krashen’s theory below further supports this concept.

2.1.3.2. The Affective Filter Hypothesis

Krashen posits that there are two separate knowledge systems for the development of competence, namely language acquisition and language learning. While acquisition refers to the natural subconscious way children pick up their first language, and possibly their second as well, “Language learning implies the conscious knowledge of language rules, which is the result of formal language instruction” (18). According to Krashen, the items acquired are those that have been able to pass through the affective filter, which consists of inhibition, motivation, personality factors etc. Conversely, the items that are learned become part of the guidance as grammatical rules and are used in production only if the speaker is focused on form and there is time to access them.

This theory states that both children and adults are able to acquire a new language, therefore, the ability to "pick-up" languages does not disappear at puberty as proposed by many other theories. Nevertheless, Krashen posits that this does not mean that adults will always achieve native-like levels in a second language, but it does imply that adults may make use of the same natural "language acquisition device" that children use.

As already mentioned, Krashen identifies two different and parallel processes: learning, which is a formal and conscious process, and acquisition, which is subconscious and natural. He further states that the way acquisition takes place is regulated by three necessary conditions: Comprehensible Input, Low/ weak Affective Filter, and Silent period. This implies that the acquirer must receive comprehensible input through reading and listening, in other words, understanding the input provided is crucial for acquisition. This input must be interesting and relevant, not grammatically sequenced, and sufficient in quantity and at the same time challenging. Krashen (19) explains that although comprehensible input is an essential condition for acquisition, it is not sufficient; there are affective requirements for language acquisition to take place.

As proposed by Miranda based on Krashen (13), the affective filter is a screen of emotion that can block language acquisition. This device seems to be responsible for the fact that some individuals can pick up a language while others cannot. Furthermore, this hypothesis tries to account for child–adult

differences, since Krashen states that the filter works in adults, but not in children. In addition to the affective filter, there is a silent period which is apparently the stage in which children, or adults, listen to people talk. This period is characterized by the assumption that while children are exposed to input, they are engaged in discovering the way language works and it provides learners with the chance to build up competence through listening. Nevertheless, in regards to Second Language Learning, Ellis (83) states that this stage is not always present since learners already have a first language and they try to speak the second language right from the start.

Affective variables such as motivation, self-confidence and anxiety could play a facilitative role in second language acquisition. As stated by Krashen, learners with high levels of motivation, self-confidence, a good self-image, and a low level of anxiety are most likely to be successful in the acquisition of a second language. On the other hand, low motivation, low self-esteem, and debilitating anxiety in combination could enhance the affective filter and form a 'mental block' that does not allow a comprehensible input to be used for language acquisition. In other words, when the affective filter is high, it prevents language acquisition from taking place.

2.1.3.3. Affective Factors and ESP

In regard to affective factors and English for Specific Purposes, the individual, in this case, the student, goes through a process of adapting himself, which can give positive and negative results, such as an increase or decrease in their motivation. Factors like eagerness, anxiety, willingness, self-awareness, and aversion to the methodology are possible results that may arise from the process. As Ulrich Schiefele states “a person in a state of being interested in a certain topic wants to learn about (or become involved with) that topic for its own sake” (304). Therefore, a student with an interest in an area would, as mentioned before, develop an individual concern for a certain topic or area of study. Ulrich also mentions that an individual interest is “conceived of as a relatively enduring preference for certain topics, subject areas or activities” (302) and that a situational interest is “an emotional state brought about by situational stimuli” (302). In broader words, it is safe to say that students’ choice will, indeed, set the path to differences in the way the students acquire a language. Due to all the above, it is clear that depending on the level of motivation the learners have (high, middle, low, non-existent), their capability of learning a language will change, and that there are external factors that will also produce variations in the emotional state of being.

During the process of learning, the individual will develop activeness when studying in the area of interest; as a result, the student will elaborate goals and objectives which would lead to encouraging their learning, this is supported by Wang and Pevery (167) when saying that “those who have the capacity for being active and independent in the learning process; they can identify goals, formulate their own goals, and can change goals to suit their own learning needs and interests; they are able to use learning strategies, and to monitor their own learning.” Concerning educational aspects, it is not possible to make an exact judgment in relation to the effect of ESP on the affective results on the learner, there is a tendency to show positive attitudes towards the subject itself; and, from our personal experience of dealing with students and children, they tend to respond more negatively to compulsory activities and obligations than when they are given choices, which can be supported by MacIntyre-Clément-Dörnyei-Noels’s (11) statement which claims “(...) when individuals decide to do something, the psychology of choice is activated. In second language learning, a speaker must have a willingness to communicate;” in the case of ESP, the language area in which the learners specialize is an area of their choice, which automatically increases their motivation, interest and, therefore, their self-confidence (Pousada 6). Furthermore, Fiorito (web) posits that when students work and learn about an area with which they are familiar, their stimulus would increase, hence the purpose of learning a language of a subject-matter would be

meaningful for them; therefore, English can be presented in contexts where language can be used for different kinds of situations.

The stakeholders are considered to be an important factor due to the fact that they are the necessary elements in the learning and teaching process. For this reason, a more in-depth analysis of these components is provided further.

2.1.4. The Stakeholders in the Learning-teaching Process

Even though it may be of obvious connotation, it is important to determine what is meant by stakeholders in the context of education, these are: “school administrators and other school personnel, school board, business leaders, elected officials, neighbor watch and youth organizations, parents and students” (web) being the latter, by far, the most important of the previously listed since they are the purpose of education as an institution.

Each of the aforementioned stakeholders play a significant role in education at different levels, all of them are correlated since they all have a role which directly and/or indirectly will benefit the other; if only one of them is left behind or is inefficient, the whole system collapses. For instance, what would happen to students and teachers if the janitor did not clean the classroom? Basic conditions to conduct a class would not be met; what would happen if there were

no students attending school? Teachers would not have a target to teach to; what would happen if administrative departments do not supervise teachers' planning processes, activities, and classes in general? The question answers itself and the point is made: stakeholders form, through their important role, this network called *education*. In other words, and as proposed by Ward, so that an institution can function correctly –and, at the same time holding the students as the target to prepare for the future—each of the stakeholders must be present and play the role they have been assigned, and focus groups must take place in order to “develop goals for the community” (4).

2.2. ELT in Chile

2.2.1. Current Situation

Nowadays, global economy is demanding people who can master more than one language. In this context, the former president of Chile Michelle Bachelet promulgated law no. 20.129 in 2006, which allows the opportunity to study abroad in an English native-speaking country for students who are in an English Teaching Program. In addition, *Inglés Abre Puertas* “English Opens Doors,” 2004, is a program created to send students from high school to study a semester in an English-speaking country school, allowing them to live an unforgettable experience. Regarding this, ex-minister Yasna Provoste said: “Everyday that goes by we become more convinced that knowing English can

make a difference. More than 2 billion people speak English around the world; the language covers 40% of the world economy jargon and 95% of the information available on the Internet (...)" 'Cada día que pasa estamos más seguros que saber inglés hace una diferencia. Más de dos mil millones de personas hablan inglés en el mundo, este idioma predomina en el 40% de la actividad económica mundial y en el 95% de la información útil que circula en Internet' (CONICYT, Web). During the year 2010, Mineduc, the body responsible for delivering nation-wide educational programs to public and subsidized schools, increased the number of English-class hours for 5th- and 6th-grade curriculums as a measure to improve the quality and learning of the students. (Edusal, web)

Gordon Cronister, exams administrator of Instituto Chileno Norteamericano de Cultura, said (Dowling, web): "Not only are the students the ones who need improvement. The teaching of English in public schools tends to be very inefficient, with overcrowded classrooms and teachers that are not qualified to teach English" 'Pero no son sólo los estudiantes quienes necesitan mejorar. La enseñanza del inglés en los colegios fiscales tiende a ser "muy mala, con salas de clase repletas y profesores que no están calificados para enseñar inglés.' This institute conducted an exam for 50 Chilean teachers whose results were in an average of 30% to 40% of qualification Cronister states that "the level was

very deficient, which is an indicator of how the country is in terms of ELT” ‘Su nivel era muy deficiente, lo que es un indicativo de cómo está el país en general.’ In addition, Fábregas (qtd. in Dowling) affirms that “(...) now we have shown that this scenario has changed and English must be taught in English (...) part of this issue is that, in the past, it was acceptable to teach English in Spanish.” ‘(...) ahora les hemos mostrado que este escenario cambió y que deben enseñar inglés en inglés (...) parte del problema es que, en el pasado, era aceptable enseñar inglés en español.’ In order to help teachers in our nation, the government has developed programs such as “English Summer Town” which is jointly developed with the Embassy of the United States. Students who are studying English can apply for a scholarship which consists in studying a semester abroad in an international institution (Business Chile, web).

As Chile is a country which is open in terms of economy, it still has challenges when facing the massive immigration of international companies. This is positive, but, the issue is that most of the Chileans do not manage to speak English; in fact, less than 2% of the Chilean labor force can speak moderate English. Thus, the Chilean government has adopted a posture to confront this issue, which will be further explained in the next chapter.

2.2.2. Government Role

During the last decades, Chile has had to face several difficulties and make changes in relation to English education and the improvement the latter needs regarding quality. For instance, as mentioned above, the program *Inglés Abre Puertas* was created to satisfy the needs –especially those related to quality— that English language was demanding in Chile, which had been an issue since before the 2000s. Not only was this measure taken in order to improve the quality of the lessons in schools, increase the numbers of hours, and make EFL mandatory in our country, but also to serve as a starting-point for many different programs directed at students, teachers, and professionals (English Opens Doors, Web). Besides, one of the latest agreements with the United States emphasizes the importance of this nation to continue to support Chile by strengthening a number of educational programs such as academic scholarships and English study-programs, among others. In actual fact, the Bureau of Western Hemisphere Affairs and the U.S. Department of State published, in March 2011, a factsheet containing details about the Trilateral Development Cooperation between the US and Chile (US Embassy, Web). In the course of former Minister of Education Joaquín Lavín in 2010, a series of tools was implemented so as to measure Chilean students' level of English. One of these tools was the English SIMCE (Sistema de Medición de la Calidad de la Educación), which seeks to measure the level of competence of Chilean students in the English language; and, it focuses its objectives on the

communicational aspects mainly, highlighting listening and reading comprehension (SIMCE, Web).

2.2.3. ELT in Schools

When analyzing ELT at a country's educational system level, it is important to analyze the various patterns that will eventually help us have a clear and objective idea on the matter. These patterns are usually, infrastructural, content-wise, students and school's scholarships, number of graduate and non-graduate teachers, budget for public schools, teacher average wages, government's investment per student (public and semi-subsidized schools), schedules, level of demand, among other patterns that may be subject of study.

The following chart provided by MINEDUC defines the level of English proficiency expected by the Chilean Government for both levels (detailed ahead) that sat for SIMCE in 2010 and also expected for teachers working in the field. These levels are determined by the Association of Language Testers of Europe (ALTE) which for this occasion adapted the standards to the reality of the Chilean ELT.

GRUPO	NIVEL ALTE
	Breakthrough
Estudiantes de 8° Básico	1: Waystage user
Estudiantes de 4 ° Medio	2: Threshold user
Profesores de Inglés	3: Independent User
	4: Competent User
	5: Good User

Table 1: English Levels Adapted by ALTE for Chilean Standards

Source: Gobierno de Chile, Min. of Educ., Mineduc; *Programa Inglés Abre Puertas - Estándares de Inglés*.

2.2.4. Current Situations of ELT Teachers

As Provoste declared (CONICYT, Web), English was and is still important to be developed in the schools in order to create new and better students, who graduate first from school, and then if they are interested in teaching, they could be more prepared if they went abroad to acquire the language in its native environment, learning more than just the language, its culture too. One of the main aims of *Inglés Abre Puertas* is to contextualize English in Chilean students'

daily life, as a better option for their future and professional decisions. It is also important to add that Chile is today a member of the OECD (Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development) in which developed countries share opinions and methods to face situations where English has gained importance.

Regarding teachers' preparation to teach a program, whether it is GE or ESP, there has been much debate. For instance, Anthony mentions that:

“Although many 'General English' teachers can be described as using an ESP approach, basing their syllabi on a learner needs analysis and their own specialist knowledge of using English for real communication, many so-called ESP teachers are using an approach far from that described above.”

(3)

With the extract above, it is possible to infer that no matter the capabilities and abilities that a General English teacher may have, there are more aspects that need to be considered at the time of teaching ESP. In addition, and as Anthony (3) mentions, the ESP teacher also finds difficulties in those specific circumstances since he is usually not very connected to the target language taught. Therefore, and as to reach the right patterns that the ESP teacher must have, Anthony mentions Dudley-Evans's description of the ESP teacher as

complying with five different characteristics or roles: 1) Teacher, 2) Collaborator, 3) Course designer and materials provider, 4) Researcher, and 5) Evaluator.

The difference does not lie in the concept of ‘teacher’ itself, but more precisely, in how the last four roles are featured in the General English teacher (Anthony 3).

2.2.5. English SIMCE the National Assessment

As it was mentioned before, the Sistema de Medición de la Calidad Educación ‘Measurement System of the Quality in Education’ (SIMCE) is an exam performed every year for the 4th, 8th and 10th grades and it covers Language, Mathematics and natural Sciences. This test was conducted for the first time in South America to evaluate English levels, which in this case only considered 11th graders. The purpose of this test was to evaluate the level of English competence across the country including communicative skills, listening and writing. MINEDUC delivered a very complete and thorough result analysis; however, only the ones important to the purpose of the present work will be considered and analyzed.

The results delivered by the test are not encouraging not only because 1 out of 10 students achieved certification, but also because of the inequality encountered in the results. For instance: 65% of the students that achieved certification have access to a more expensive and parametrically better education; as displayed in the following chart designed by MINEDUC.

Chart 1: Source: Chile, CEDUS; *Resultados SIMCE Inglés 2010, 3° Educación Media*; 2010; PDF file 8.

Chart 2: Source: Chile, CEDUS; *Resultados SIMCE Inglés 2010, 3° Educación Media*; 2010; PDF file 9.

The inequality evident in the first chart is even more notable in the following one in which the results are separated into administrative dependencies: public, subsidized and private schools, categories that in Chile generally carry different quality standards.

The figures above are the main reason why the present work is carried out. It is the live image of inequality in the education of the country and the reason why

the instruments of the present study were applied to the sector that does not belong to the 64% displayed above. Nevertheless, ELT does not only take place within the school system but also outside it, hence, the following item.

2.2.6. ELT outside the School System

Before going any further into this item, it is important to recall that the teaching of ESP is, indeed, part of ELT, and its existence directly derives from it.

In Chile, outside the school system, there are various ELT programs across the country in language institutes and universities. Among the universities, it is possible to find programs that include English as one of their courses. Presumably, the English included in such programs is taught to develop English related to different areas such as law, tourism hospitality, engineering, geology engineering, geology, merchant marine engineering, maritime transportation engineering, and ecotourism, among others (UNAB, web). In regard to some institutes, there are different programs offering various types of courses. For instance, Instituto Chileno Norteamericano offers English for Interpersonal Communication and English for Personal Development (web). There are also institutes focused on specific programs such as English for U.N peace missions which is directed to the military; English for Pilots and Air Controllers and English for Business (Tronwell Institute, Web). The ELT situation outside the school system in Chile has many options to offer apart from ESP programs,

such as teaching English as a complementary resource for schools, making students able to maintain conversations with others in English (Instituto Chileno Norteamericano, web).

As it can be seen, the current ELT context in schools is not complying with the standards that the MINEDUC requires; therefore, many students have been looking for complementary programs so as to reinforce their level of English. As researchers, we have been witnesses that schools do not have the resources (material and manpower) to give students the necessary tools to either communicate in English effectively or understand it. In the following chapter, ESP worldwide is going to be analyzed in terms of how it is used for educational (tertiary) or business purposes in different countries.

2.3. ESP

2.3.1. ESP Worldwide

English for Specific Purposes is spread worldwide in the continents of the globe (Africa, America, Asia, Europe, and Oceania), as Fortanet-Gómez and Räisänen (26) say: “in several countries, e.g. Finland, Germany, and to a certain extent Sweden, ESP is taught by language centers affiliated to the universities.” In the United Kingdom, as well as in other English speaking countries such as Australia, Canada, New Zealand, and the United States of America, there are also institutions that follow ESP tenets in language teaching. In Asia, countries

such as China have implemented ESP courses after the country entered the World Trade Organization (WTO) (Li, Web).

From the literature review, it has been possible to reach certain conclusions. One of these is the fact that ESP is currently being assessed in tertiary context. For instance, a comprehensive study was conducted at Aizu University in Japan in which clear-cut differences between English for General Purposes (EGP) and ESP are established in order to set the ground rules for an eventual ESP application in the aforementioned institution (Orr, Web). This study was conducted in the year 1998, and although thirteen years have gone by, unfortunately, the results have not been reported. In spite of international studies (such as the one mentioned above), discussions, and the benefits that ESP programs grant, only a few have actually been implemented around the world – and only at tertiary level.

2.3.1.1. Importance of ESP

In order to set ESP and its preponderance within foreign language teaching, David Carter (qtd. in Gatehouse, web) labelled in 1983 all of the areas that must be covered in order for an individual to acquire a foreign or second language; ESP is indeed one of those areas as described in the following list:

- English as a restricted language.
- English for Academics and Occupational Purposes.

- English with specific topics.

Some derivations that can be made from the three types are business, technical, scientific, social, academic, investigation among other more specific areas that diverge from our main interest.

As aforementioned, ESP is centered on the language appropriate to activities in terms of grammar, lexis, register, study skills, discourse and genre. Therefore, an ESP teacher needs specific methodologies, tools, and strategies to be prepared to give quality ESP lessons. Thus, students who are taking the ESP course of their interest would be able to use the language acquired as a tool in their professional and academic fields.

With regards to having an ESP program in the Chilean high school system, Carter's third definition, English for specific topics, goes hand in hand with the idea of the present researchers since it seems only logical that the areas of specificity should be the ones chosen by the students in the Chilean education, namely Humanities (Sociology, Philosophy), History, Science (Biology and Chemistry), Maths and Physics, Arts, and Information and Communication Technology (ICT).

The importance of ESP is that it would be in accordance with the students' needs, for instance, it can be a useful tool for work or for academic purposes. Regarding the local situation, the literature reviewed has shown data to support the idea of the importance of knowing English at work. However, Dudley-Evans (qtd. in Gatehouse) states that ESP is targeted at professional work situations. On the one hand, Chile has subscribed Free Trade Agreements with English-speaking countries which imply personnel working in the export-import area to learn English or just have a basic level of it in order to communicate with people from other nations. Knowing English to be used in the national context is not the only option, it can also be used in other countries and in several working situations, for instance, working in a cruise or in a hotel implies the acquisition of English for specific situations. On the other hand, learning English with a specific approach would also give the individual a tool to handle texts or literature in written English, this principally occurs in universities where English is taught both as part of a syllabus or as an optional program.

As a conclusion, ESP is important when dealing with specific situations whether it is for work or academic purposes. Moreover, it is a complementary tool for students who want to specialize in specific areas.

Below, countries where ESP is implemented will be analyzed in terms of its application and outcomes. Some countries have already adopted ESP in tertiary education, and in some other cases it has been studied for its future implementation.

2.3.1.2. Countries in Which ESP is Implemented

Some of the countries in which ESP programs are currently being taught are Ukraine, Germany, Finland, Sweden, and Morocco, among others; and, the method under which these programs work is, in most cases, controlled by language centers affiliated to universities; and, in order to give a factual account of which results ESP gives and reflects on the participants of the educational context, some aspects related to reactions and attitude towards ESP abroad are going to be reviewed.

Unfortunately, there is not much evidence of ESP implemented as a full official program; therefore, it is difficult to find literature related to the topic. However, it is possible to find information about ESP as a program in universities worldwide. For instance, Mohamad Abdulhamed (9) describes a study done by Yassin Ibrahim titled “Doctor and Patient Questions as a Measure of Doctor Centredness in UAE Hospitals” that in the United Arab Emirates, there is EMP (English for Medical Purposes) specially designed for communicational purposes. He states that it is more important to include speaking and listening

activities rather than reading and writing. This can be explained by mentioning that the United Arab Emirates's program seeks to develop a communicational process between nurses, doctors, and patients.

In the case of Costa Rica, Universidad Nacional is creating a branch of ESP. "(...) to achieve a place in the global economy, the government settled on multiple initiatives to allow its citizens different opportunities to learn English (...)" For instance, Costa Rica has been interested in receiving international investments, due to this, the country aims to train ESP teachers in order to teach English in specific areas. According to Saborio and Valenzuela (392) "The demand for employees with proficiency in English for general purposes (EGP) was exceeded in recent years by the demand for individuals who besides having command of EGPs were proficient in English for specialized purposes (ESP)."

2.3.1.3. The Stakeholders' Attitude Towards ESP

Unquestionably, English has become the main tool to communicate in every-day life, but, more importantly, in the workplace. This is the reason why decision-makers in the education sector, specifically in language institutions, have begun redesigning and reformulating the way their programs have been working so far. For instance, one of Morocco's main interests is to specialize the professionals in English for the hospitality industry, which is an important economic sector for

this country, by providing them a solid and useful language for the area of work in which they are involved. To do this, several reforms have already taken place in recent years, yet none of which have given progressive or factually positive results. Thus, a strong worry amongst the responsible for efficient ELT and ESP programs is the search for the appropriate teaching methods that make English useful and purposeful for the students and future professionals, so that they can exploit this resource as fully as possible (Bouzidi 1).

Similarly to the situation in Morocco, Ukrainian higher education has had to face troublesome periods. During the year 2005, Ukrainian professionals, with the approval of the Ministry of Education and Science, developed an ESP program which was focused on satisfying the needs of Ukrainian students and the European Higher Education Area's (EHEA) demands for better quality and higher levels of English language in the future generations, and, in order to comply with various factors of international nature which go from professional and global development to the mere usage of the language. As Havrylyuk-Yensen and Kuran (Dean and Head of Department of Ternopil National Economic University, respectively) state in their article "Ukraine: English for Specific Purposes (ESP) Curriculum Reforming Processes":

This was done: 1) as a response to international developments; 2) In order to meet the language needs of university students across a range

of discipline areas; 3) to provide benchmarks for teachers and students in line with the levels identified in Common European Framework of Reference (CEF); and 4) to provide a standardized basis for course and syllabus design by teachers of English at the faculty level in universities throughout Ukraine.

(Havrylyuk-Yensen and Kuran 1)

Besides the background information on overseas stakeholders' attitude and reactions towards ESP explained above, similar aspects that take place in the Arab world must also be clarified so as to have an objective perspective about the situation in different countries of the world. It is important to mention that around twenty-two countries located in Northeast Africa and Western Asia comprise the Arab world (The Economist, Web). Ouakrime, professor at Sidi Mohamed Ben Abdellah University in Fez, Morocco, developed a paper for the *Proceedings of the XVIIth MATE Annual Conference* in 1997. One of the key aims of his work was to provide the perceptions that teachers have towards ESP programs. Ouakrime (12) elaborates that teachers –in public schools- have hesitancy towards ESP; the instructors believe that having an ESP program involves time consumption in terms of designing and elaborating a course. Besides that, teachers insist on the demands of having knowledge in the area of the students' specialization; however, teachers in the private sector do not show any hesitation about ESP as an alternative teaching approach. In addition, the

author states that there is no ESP tradition, in other words, he says that ESP is not commonly acknowledged in the ELT context. Therefore, institutions where this teaching methodology is applied are not widely considered within the conventional ELT in given countries.

2.3.1.4. Main Findings on the Contributions of ESP to ELT

Given the fact that ESP programs have not been widely promoted in the Chilean local arena apart from tertiary education and the private sector, little is known of its characteristics. Therefore, a common assumption that may arise is that since it focuses on the target language of a certain subject, it should actually take less class hours. For instance, as Fiorito states, an ESP program would reduce the amount of time in learning due to the fact that it is content-based; there is no focus on grammar or language structure (web). It is important to bear in mind that an ESP program focuses on the very specific use of the language and on the learners' interests. Thus, the time spent on learning would be reduced because the main objective is to teach the target content; and, additionally, to be more precise, an ESP program will be complementary in the sense that it aims at satisfying both the specialized, more technical language and the more colloquial language needs (Fiorito, web). Since ESP reduces the time allotted to the learning-teaching process, it may be assumed that it could act as a content-reducer, however, this is not so; but rather it reformulates the

way in which contents are taught, exposing students to contents and their use explicitly and more practically –avoiding the typical, prosaic lectures given in a grammar class. In addition, it is important to highlight the fact that an ESP program aims at exposing the students to the specific language –and, more importantly, *jargon*—which will become their main tool of verbal communication in their professional area of work. Additionally, students that already have an English proficiency would immediately benefit from an ESP program since it would motivate them to study in their area of interest (Fiorito, web) In other words, ESP should be seen as simply another approach towards teaching or as Hutchinson says: “an approach to language teaching in which all decisions as to content and method are based on the learner's reason for learning" (qtd. in Gatehouse, web).

2.3.2. ESP in Chile

English has become more and more important in today's world, so many people have started to consider English as a means to increase their job opportunities. However, in countries such as Chile, where English is taught as a foreign language, there are no substantial opportunities to learn English for Specific Purposes, or, at least, gain more in-depth knowledge about the area in which people are interested, developing or specializing. However, it was said

earlier that some of the English courses included in university programs are apparently aiming at satisfying specific needs.

During the development of the present work, an exhaustive search of possible contexts in which ESP traits could be found was made in order to provide factual information and the real contexts existing in Chile. However, and, despite the many visits made to various places, one conclusion was reached: there is no official program implemented nationwide, more specifically as a school program; nonetheless, ESP traits could, in fact, be found in tertiary-education centers.

As a result of the visits made to different institutions, it was possible to find one common aspect: The majority of these institutions teach ESP programs based on course-books published by well-known English and American press. One of the visits made was to a large and prestigious language center (not only English) located in Las Condes, Santiago where different ESP programs such as English for Peace Missions, English for Business, and English for Pilots and Air-Traffic Controllers are taught. In addition to the previous information obtained, one of the most prominent private universities in Chile with campuses in the coast, south, and capital city includes ESP in some of their programs. For instance, the Business Administration program of the institution mentioned above uses Pearson Longman's *Market Leader*.

Having concluded a review of the literature regarding ESP and related topics, it is possible to start building the study that will provide the data needed in order to reach the target of the present work, namely, to determine whether the requirements to implement an ESP program are present in the Chilean high-school reality.

3. CHAPTER THREE: THE STUDY

3.1. Objectives

General Objective:

- To determine whether EFL standards at high-school levels in Chile allow a potential incorporation of ESP into the classroom, by studying the factors involved in the implementation of an ELT program and in the process of learning.

Specific Objectives:

- To analyze ESP requirements of application in regards to international educational context. This is to determine who ESP is aimed at, the level of English the users must have, and the areas of study with which the target students have to be familiarized.
- To determine why ESP does not widely take a primordial role in the Chilean education.
- To determine how the stakeholders in the educational process view the elements that define ESP.

3.2. Hypothesis

WORKING HYPOTHESES

- More than 80% of the participants believe the English taught at school needs a change.
- ESP programs require a high level of English previously acquired.
- More than 60% percent of the participants see ESP as positive and contributing to the learning of English and as a purposeful tool.
- More than 30% of the students see the English they are being taught as a purposeful tool.

NULL HYPOTHESES

- Less than 80% of the participants believe the English taught at school needs a change.
- ESP programs do not require a high level of English previously acquired.
- Less than 60% percent of the participants see ESP as positive and contributing to the learning of English.

Less than 30% of the students see the English they are being taught as a purposeful tool.

3.3. Type of Research Study

The present work has a descriptive aim, in which several patterns related to each other will be analyzed quantitatively and qualitatively; therefore, a mixed approach is needed to conduct this investigation because the main interest is to get statistical data of the students', teachers', and administrative board's perspectives on the ELT reality nowadays. Firstly, the questionnaires are qualitative in the sense that they are aimed at showing the perspective of the stakeholders in the ELT field by the selection they make during the surveys and the explanations that they provide. All this information is of valuable nature because it is provided by the protagonists of education. Secondly, this research aims at providing statistical information which is displayed in charts so as to have a numerical idea of the factors that are being analyzed, and, which are of significant importance to reach a results analysis.

3.4. Variables

The term “variable” is more commonly used in psychology; however it may be applied in other contexts and processes. According to the psychologist Kendra Cherry “a variable is something that can be changed, such as a characteristic or value. Variables are generally used to determine if changes to one thing result in changes to another” (Psychology About, web) or ‘las variables adquieren valor para la investigación... cuando llegan a relacionarse con otras hipótesis’

“variables acquire importance for the investigation they relate to other hypotheses” (Hérmendez, Roberto, Carlos Fernández, and Pilar Baptista, 12) In any process, especially in education, many phenomena will directly or indirectly affect the other. For education to take place, several conditions must be granted to achieve certain results. For instance, more or less resources will result in better or worse education, however, that will depend on the pedagogical skills of the teachers from a given school or on the willingness of the students. These variables escape the norm, since normally schools with more resources result in better schools, nevertheless, some poor schools around the world have been known to breed brilliant students only based on methodologies and learning systems for which neither resources nor technologies are needed. A clear example of this can be found in Chile; the *Escuelas Efectivas* ‘Effective Schools’ are schools located in very poor areas of the cities whose students are of similar or same characteristics, regardless, the students achieve high standards of education and graduate to be professionals or successful workers. The latter further clarifies that variables in education cannot be generalized but that in other cases changes can be observed after the application of modifications. Although the present study is not experimental, in order to make clear the different elements we will assess, we have defined the following variables:

- Perception about the current state of ELT
- Current situation of ELT

- Perception about ESP
- Stakeholders' willingness towards including ESP as part of the syllabi
- Students' awareness of the importance of English

3.5. Methodological Framework

The methodological framework is perhaps the most important tool from which objective and truthful information may be gathered. It will grant the actual information regarding the topic of the current work, which is to understand and learn the main stakeholder's point of view regarding EFL in Chile and the question whether a change is needed or not. As it is stated earlier in this work, all stakeholders in education are equally important, however, in a study conducted in Italy it was concluded that "students become the protagonists of their own learning while teachers are facilitators" (Cardano 1). The last statement makes clear the fact that all stakeholders are important but that all efforts are focused towards one of them: students. This is the reason why the instruments (surveys) of the present study were mainly applied to students.

After studying all contexts of education in Chile considering aspects such as economic, social and school-location; it was determined that the institutions in which more meaningful changes regarding EFL are needed are: public, semi-subsidized, municipal and schools that belong to non-profit educational

organizations meant to help vulnerable students who otherwise would not have the chance to study. Unfortunately, in Chile these characteristics result in poor quality education at all levels and especially EFL, since it is useful in contexts where more resources are usually needed (technology, flying abroad, etc.). This is the context where the instruments were applied in order to obtain data from stakeholders who are protagonists in the educative environment mentioned above which according to the studies, lack the correct elements to achieve successful results. These students who receive this education are the ones meant to manifest their satisfaction or dissatisfaction through the instrument provided.

Based on the information provided by the MINEDUC and SIMCE in English studies, the following facts were able to be concluded: Of the top 20 schools with better results, eighteen are private schools located in districts known to belong to high-class families and are bilingual and have very high enrolment and monthly fees.

In this investigation, there is one main method used to collect the data needed – and the reason why it is used is the following: surveys: this type of data-collection tool is applied in order to identify the stakeholders' interests in English as a subject. It also gives more detailed information on areas of study that may

be interesting for the students. For this, the survey is in Spanish and the questions are easy to understand and answer; it is important to avoid misconceptions; therefore, no difficult questions were asked so as not to confuse the students, the teachers, or any of the board members. Through the analysis of the surveys answered it is possible to reach conclusions and perceptions that the stakeholders have regarding the English language nowadays.

3.5.1. Participants

In order to get statistical results that represent an average Chilean school, it was necessary not to include private schools in the investigation. Some of the reasons why the mentioned criterion was considered are that 1) private schools do not represent the educational reality in Chile, 2) most private schools offer their students many more hours of English per week in comparison to the other schools, and 3) private-schools students are usually raised in high-income households which by far do not represent the average Chilean reality.

Since the present investigation focuses on the education-related stakeholders, they are now explained:

- 1) Students: eleventh-graders were selected since there are clearer analyses of the English SIMCE tests they have taken in the past. The

students are the main –and the source for an ESP program—and most important element to be analyzed since the investigation itself is focused on them. Therefore, connections and diagnoses can be conducted with the use of available data in order to have a more objective view of ELT. A total number of 128 students was surveyed in all the schools.

2) Teachers are one of the main actors of education. They are the ones who transmit contents and values to the students to the point that a teacher can determine the course of a person's life. We have selected teachers of English from an average reality, which are primarily middle-low socio-economic schools. The survey aims at reflecting the teachers' opinions towards ELT today in Chile, emphasizing its strong and weak aspects. The total number of teachers is 6.

3) Administrative members: boards are comprised of people that organize and elaborate all the aspects that make an educational institution work providing appropriate intrapersonal, interpersonal, and educational atmosphere. Administrative members' perspective regarding ELT and ESP is also displayed and explained in the results analysis. A total number of 4 administrative members participated in the survey.

3.5.2. Procedure

In order to clearly illustrate the procedures which allowed the information to be obtained during the process of investigation, an explanation of the different stages is mentioned below:

Firstly, it was necessary to design and elaborate data-collection instruments that aimed at both showing tendencies and also perceptions of the different target group for this investigation. To do so, three different surveys were elaborated: 1) the “Encuesta Administrativos,” 2) “Encuesta Profesores,” and 3) “Encuesta Alumnos.” These three models differ in the objectives to be reached. For instance, in no. 1 administrative boards explain their view on English teaching and the results they expect for their students; on the other hand, in no. 3 students themselves explain what they expect from learning English and their view about the subject itself. Secondly, the authors thought it was necessary to approach every school’s director first and ask them for permission, directly, so as to follow the appropriate ethical procedure. In addition, it is the directors who are the representative image of a school. After the respective approval from each of the directors, an appointment was granted for the authors of this investigation by the authorities of the each schools, which led to the survey-conduction in 11th grade.

Procedures Objective 1

To describe ESP requirements of application in regard of international educational context in terms of target students, level of English, and areas of study in the foreign institutions that will be mentioned.

Even though not much material on ESP can be found most of information was obtained thanks to the deep study of American and European researcher, teachers and institutions dedicated to the finding of new methodologies.

Procedures Objective 2

To describe ESP requirements of application in regard of Chilean educational context in terms of target students, level of English, and areas of study with which the target students have to be familiarized in some of the Chilean institutions where ESP programs may be taught.

It was learned on the one hand, that knowledge wise, nothing is previously needed for a possible ESP application, however, on the other hand some experts determined that ESP requires certain basic knowledge of English. To reach conclusions regarding this specific objective it was necessary to study both ESP deeply and the Chilean current state of education as well. Plenty of literature, rates and analyses were available to do so, especially on Chilean education.

Procedures Objective 3

To determine why ESP does not widely take a significant role in the Chilean education.

Actually, ESP does not take a significant role in Chile or in the world. Even though many studies have been conducted, ESP as an education trend has not received much attention from teaching entities around the globe and certainly not in Chile, perhaps only at tertiary level. As mentioned earlier, ESP is not widely spread as other trends like general English or kinesthetic learning, etc. It was determined empirically and by simple literature study that ESP is not relevant; however, further experimental studies must be held to reach deeper conclusion.

Procedures Objective 4

To determine how the stakeholders in the educational process view ESP.

To achieve this objective the surveys were fundamental. Since there were no available ones, three different surveys were delivered for the 3 main stakeholders of education (students, teacher, administrative personnel). They were the ones to give objective view of the elements that define ESP.

The surveys were displayed on a sheet of paper in a given classroom of each school. The students were either complete classes or a mixed selection of students from different classes. An approximate number of 130 students were

surveyed and a brief explanation of ESP was given to the students before the surveys were conducted.

In order to give a clear account of the information gathered, the results of the surveys will be displayed in 5 sections corresponding to the answers obtained in the 5 schools. This information will be displayed in graphs followed by an analysis per question. In addition, on assessing the questionnaires answered by the students, the researchers realized the existence of a variable that had not been taken into consideration at the start. This variable is related to the mood or willingness in which the students answered. Here the completeness and quality of the answers were taken into consideration and it was decided to analyze this variable and include it in our results since it would reflect to a certain degree the interest the students have on the topic.

3.5.3. Legal Framework

The present work was directly related to the investigation and analysis of the different factors that are involved in a given context –particularly the current status of ELT at high-school levels in Chile—and in specific schools. This led the authors of this research to cling to the respective patterns with which a professional, serious, and academic piece of work is connected.

Concerning ethical aspects, the present research paper has a special consideration for the cultural diversity that may be encountered during the investigation. The finality of the investigation is not to create any kind of problem during the process of collecting data. Therefore, social awareness is one of the most important factors to have in mind when conducting the research with people with different cultural points of view. Besides, regarding the approval in relation to the investigation, this is very necessary since we, as researchers, will need permission of the school-board in order to conduct our research, and, in this way obtain the data needed to support and develop the problem in this document and in any further investigation. Having taken into account the ethical considerations, we did not inform the participants about the research. As investigators, it is thought that notifying the participants about the investigation may change their perspective about certain topics, so it has been determined to collect the data in a way that participants give unspoiled answers to the questions. Since the students are subjects under the school care and supervision, the school-board is the body that allows us to visit different classes that will be part of the investigation prior to us informing the school about the objectives of the research.

Furthermore, the research will be performed with professional reliability. That is the reason why objectivity is one of the main aims of the investigation due to the

fact that it is a research that is going to be conducted seriously and without any kind of bias. The investigation is the determination to be truthful and having no tendency to be inclined towards a posture of any kind. What is more, names of schools may be changed or protected so as not to affect their image as a result of academic investigation.

Unquestionably, our investigation avoids any kind of misinterpretation or deception, and, instead, it focuses exclusively on using the data collected regarding the quality of the English language taught in schools.

At the same time, the confidentiality of the data collected is an important feature in the process and the study will not reveal information that may affect the subjects of investigation.

3.5.4. Statistical Analysis

Double entry tables will be used for the recording and later analysis of the data obtained and the following statistical procedures will be performed:

1. The answers to the surveys will be quantified, averaged, and compared among five schools.
2. Totals and percentages will be calculated to give account of opinions and perceptions regarding the various items in the surveys.

3. Data obtained will be compared with the existing literature where possible.

Given the factors that will be statistically analyzed, it is now possible to begin considering the results and what these imply in regard to the objectives and the main purpose of the present work.

3.6. Results

In the chart displayed below it will be possible to see the mood with which students answered the survey, this will grant a general idea of how important they consider English in their context and whether they consider it necessary for their lives. Students who answer interestingly will evidently provide a full and committed answer, whereas half-answered sheets will show no interest or low levels of commitment towards the subject. It is important to mention that the survey was conducted during a time where students are considered to be at their best so as to decrease external conditions that could result in students answering uninterestedly, these modifying conditions are: hunger, stress, heat, tiredness, among others.

Before illustrating any statistical data, it is important to show the mood of the students to whom the instruments were applied and the importance and relevance they gave to this task. The latter will be shown as percentages

reflecting the students' mood perceived when answering the surveys. So as to get the most approximate information, it was necessary to count each part of the questions in the survey. For example, question no. 1 has two parts: the alternative and the writing gap; questions like no. 2 consists of only 1 part. See *table 2* to get a clearer idea.

Q1		Q 2	Q 3		Q 4		Q 5	Q 6	Q 7	Q 8	
Alternative	Writing gap	Alternative	Alternative	Writing gap	Alternative	Writing gap	Alternative	Alternative	Alternative	Alternative	Writing gap

Table 2: Survey layout

As shown in the table, the students' survey consists of twelve parts. In order to analyze a student's mood when answering a survey, we first counted the number of answered parts, and, then, illustrated that amount in percentages. For example, if 'student 1' answered only 7 parts, that resulted in 58.3% completion.

The following percentages were perceived from the different schools:

- School A showed an average of 98.3% completion.
- School B showed an average of 94.3% completion.
- School C showed an average of 98% completion, being the institution that reflected the highest interest.
- School D showed an average of 85% completion.

- School E showed an average of 90% completion.

The results show a very high interest from the students in general and this is represented by 91.8% completion rate, making it more than $\frac{3}{4}$ of the total. To see the tables used, see *appendix I*.

“School A”: Analysis of the questions.

Chart School A: School in the Fourth Region, Student’s answers

QUESTION 1

- 1) Do you think the current situation of English teaching needs a change?
 - a) Yes
 - b) No

As it is possible to interpret, students have a tendency to demonstrate a positive reaction towards the current ELT situation through 77% approval. In other words, this means that the participants of this survey are satisfied with the state of English teaching in that specific school. However, there is also a negative reaction towards the ELT situation; this can be interpreted as the students have a degree of disappointment with the present situation of ELT. Answers such as “debiera mejorar” ‘it should improve’ and “porque deberían ser más dinámicas

para incentivar a los alumnos” ‘because it should be more dynamic in order to motivate students’ it can be inferred that there is a concern about the Chilean reality in terms of the English teaching in school nation-wide.

QUESTION 2

2) Do you think English is important for your job in the future?

- a) Very important
- b) Important
- c) Not very important
- d) Doesn't have any importance at all

As it is possible to interpret, 46% of the students have a tendency to show that English is important in their future work. Therefore, it would be possible to say that participants have acknowledged that English is a language that is useful. Nonetheless, there are students who have a different point of view about English as a tool in the future. This could mean that they might not consider English as useful. In fact, 17% percent of them believe it is not very important.

QUESTION 3

3) Would you like the English you learn to be focused on your tertiary or professional/working interests?

a) Yes

b) No

When interpreting this chart, the participants have a tendency at considering ESP as a new way to learn English. 80% the applicants would like to have their English lessons focused on their interests; answers like “sería útil en lo académico y laboral” ‘it would be useful in the academic and working issues’ means that ESP would give them a tool for facing new challenges to study not only a program in which English related to their area is taught, but also books and different types of sources of information available only in English. Nevertheless, there are students who would not like English to be focused on their academic or work interests. By interpreting this, it can be said that the participants would prefer having the present English taught in schools. Answers such as “debe enfocarse en el día a día” ‘it should be focused on a daily-basis’ demonstrates that their main interest is to learn English that would be useful for them in a daily-basis context.

QUESTION 4

4) Do you think an ESP program would give you the necessary tools to achieve a better quality future job?

a) Yes

b) No

Considering the results obtained for question 4, it is possible to state that there is a tendency (77%) to think of ESP as a tool to make future work situations better for the participants. They think that attending and learning in an ESP course would be of benefit. However, there are students who do not believe ESP to be an important tool for developing inside the job market; this may mean that the applicants do not have a concept of the importance of English in Chile due to the globalization factor that is everyday increasing in our Chilean society.

QUESTION 5

5) If there were a Specific English program, which area(s) would you choose?

- a) Science (Chemistry/biology)
- b) Mathematics (Physics and Mathematics)
- c) Art
- d) Humanities (Sociology and Philosophy).
- e) History.

Interpreting the data collected from question 5, it can be seen that there are different interests, there is no dominating tendency represented in the chart. For instance, this says that if an ESP program was implemented in schools, it should have varieties. The variety of ESP courses depends on the students' interests

and aims. This was represented through percentages not far from each other, being the highest 30% and the lowest 10%.

QUESTION 6

- 6) How many hours of English do you have per week?
- a) 2 hours
 - b) 3 hours
 - c) 4 hours
 - d) 5 hours
 - e) 6 hours or more

According to the data provided by this question, most of the students have 4 hours of English, whereas there are other students who have 6 hours. This reflects that English is not as important in the school curriculum as in other ones as the chart shows that only 20% of the students have at least 6 hours.

QUESTION 7

- 7) If you had a Specific English program, how many hours of English would you like to have per week?
- a) 2 hours
 - b) 3 hours
 - c) 4 hours
 - d) 5 hours
 - e) 6 hours or more

This chart shows that most of the students would like to have 2 to 4 hours of an ESP course regarded by 33%, which means 1/3. By interpreting this; it is possible to infer that most of the students have some kind of interest in attending an ESP course; however, the students were asked what amount of time for English they would like to have by choosing 2, 4, 6 or more hours. Most of them chose 2 hours, and then the other tendency was 4 hours. The information

collected in question no. 7 shows that students willing to be under an ESP program.

QUESTION 8

- 8) If you had a Specific English program, do you think you would learn
- a) Much more
 - b) Some more
 - c) A little more
 - d) Very little more

In question 8, the results show that most of the participants have a positive judgment of ESP, a representative 63%. The tendency shows that most of the students believe they would learn more if they had ESP programs in their schools. This might mean that having ESP programs in the Chilean education system would be significant for the students.

“School B”: Analysis of the questions.

Charts School B: School in Santiago D.C., Student’s answers

School B is located in East-Santiago. It is in a district that has one of the highest rates of delinquency, poverty, teenage pregnancy, school desertion and social segregation levels in Santiago and in Chile.

QUESTION 1

- 1) Do you think the current situation of English teaching needs a change?
 - a) Yes
 - b) No

In the present question, the students answered and gave their opinions on their perception about the current state of ELT in Chile and whether it needs a change at any level, or not. The pie chart provides us with the idea that a large part of the students (72%) agreed with the fact that Chilean ELT needs a change which may be linked with their disconformities and need for better ELT

education. Also, in many of their written answers they manifest their necessity for better English since it will be useful in the future.

QUESTION 2

2) Do you think English is important for your job in the future?

- a) Very important
- b) Important
- c) Not very important
- d) Doesn't have any importance at all

Almost as a continuance from chart number 1, the students demonstrate interest towards ELT. In fact 82% of them, as seen in the chart, stated that English will indeed be important for their future. The latter provides us with the idea that ELT must be improved, especially in schools with low resources, in which according to most rates and rankings English is not being correctly taught and need a change and improvement in order to serve students' wishes and needs. The few

students that manifested no importance explained that there are jobs that do not have any English matters involved.

QUESTION 3

3) Would you like the English you learn to be focused on your tertiary or professional/working interests?

a) Yes

b) No

The results of the current question are very promising for the objective of this paper since it demonstrates that 19% of students from this specific school would be interested in dedicating at least some hours of ESP in their program. It also shows a clear need from the students to focus their English knowledge on the areas that they would be interested in and as studied earlier increase their motivation and interest towards the subject.

QUESTION 4

- 4) Do you think an ESP program would give you the necessary tools to achieve a better quality future job?
- a) Yes
 - b) No

This answer percentage supports chart number 3 by 97%. It represents even further the belief from students that specialization through ESP methodologies is an aid towards reaching better English learning and results. In Chile it is known that English opens doors to better jobs or it is a plus when it comes to seeking them many times preferring the presence of English in a curriculum over better diplomas at better educational institutions.

QUESTION 5

5) If there were a Specific English program, which area(s) would you choose?

- a) Science (Chemistry/biology)
- b) Mathematics (Physics and Mathematics)
- c) Art
- d) Humanities (Sociology and Philosophy).
- e) History.

Even though some areas are predominant in the chart (33%), it is possible to determine that students' interests are diverse and that in the case of an eventual ESP implementation it will be necessary to cover as many areas of interest as possible, so as to satisfy most of the students' needs even in areas with only 3%.

QUESTION 6

6) How many hours of English do you have per week?

- a) 2 hours
- b) 3 hours
- c) 4 hours
- d) 5 hours
- e) 6 hours or more

In this chart it is possible to see some discrepancy which may be because of the students' lack of interest in answering. There is not much to analyze in this chart since students are simply asked about the amounts English subject hours they have in their school. The answer should indeed be 100%; however the different answers can be explained by the students' mistakes, lack of interest or confusion.

QUESTION 7

- 7) If you had a Specific English program, how many hours of English would you like to have per week?
- a) 2 hours
 - b) 3 hours
 - c) 4 hours
 - d) 5 hours
 - e) 6 hours or more

In this chart it is possible to see different variables. Half (49%) the students found that 4 hours of ESP was enough to meet their needs, this clarified of course in many of their explanations, that ESP would be better as complementary of general English since it is also necessary for daily communicative situations. On the other hand, some students would like to have

a minimum amount of ESP hours and other 6 or more hours; this depends on their personal interest and motivation.

QUESTION 8

- 8) If you had a Specific English program, do you think you would learn
- a) Much more
 - b) Some more
 - c) A little more
 - d) Very little more

Another chart that is very important for our interest regarding ESP. An important part of students (83%) manifested that they would learn more if ESP was implemented at their schools. This answer also reflects the need for an English teaching method that may improve and increase the will to learn that they have shown not only in the present questionnaire.

“School C”: Analysis of the questions.

Charts School C: School in Santiago D.C., Student’s answers

School C is a technical school which comprises students raised in low-income families in the metropolitan area and who often receive benefits from the Ministry of Education.

The following pie charts show the amount of students that answered each questions. The following information is shown as percentages.

QUESTION 1

- 1) Do you think the current situation of English teaching needs a change?
 - a) Yes
 - b) No

It shows a clear tendency (85%) to the “Yes, the English taught needs a change,” and it can be interpreted from the explanations provided by the students of this particular school that they do not see the English subject as a motivating course. In fact, the explanations provided suggest that English has many, serious flaws. For instance, aspects like demotivating English takes a major role in this question; then, students also mention the fact that they need more hours of English if they want to succeed, or that the English they are being taught is too basic and purposeless. This, indeed, reflects a disappointment towards the subject and a dissatisfaction towards the learning itself. However, it can be inferred that teachers are one of the main causalities since, as just mentioned, students give some details about the boredom experienced in class. Besides this, two direct opinions from the students are “la educación es de mala calidad,” and “porque deberían ser más dinámicas para incentivar a los alumnos,” putting emphasis on the methodological aspect of teaching.

QUESTION 2

2) Do you think English is important for your job in the future?

- a) Very important
- b) Important
- c) Not very important
- d) Doesn't have any importance at all

In question 2, students project themselves into the future and choose how important they think English would be for their future jobs. As a matter of fact, more than half of the students (almost $\frac{3}{4}$) believe that the English language plays a very significant role in their professional lives (option a: very important), while 29% of the students surveyed said that it plays a significant role in their future, professional lives (option b: important). This part of the interview reflects

the students' expectations towards mastering the English language orally. It can be interpreted that although the students may seem to be disappointed with the methods teachers use inside the classroom, they do believe and insist that the English language they are taught in their schools should be subject to discussion and analysis.

QUESTION 3

3) Would you like the English you learn to be focused on your tertiary or professional/working interests?

a) Yes

b) No

Students are clearly in favor of being exposed to purposeful English. Ninety-five percent of the students claim that the English which they are studying at school must target their own specialties, making English, as recently expressed, purposeful. A great number of the students (95%) claimed at this stage that “de

ésta forma perfeccionaría mi especialidad,” which shows the importance of it for students of technical high-schools.

Besides the previously mentioned, students state that being taught an ESP program would result in countless benefits concerning work aspects. For instance, many of them (95%) say that mastering this target language might lead to finding a job much faster and to much more developed capability to certainly use it in work situations.

Nonetheless, five percent of the answers in question 3 express the idea that being immersed in an ESP program is meaningless since it would not fit the current country’s contexts and needs.

QUESTION 4

4) Do you think an ESP program would give you the necessary tools to achieve a better quality future job?

- a) Yes
- b) No

Undoubtedly, question 4 is the clearest result of all (97%). Only three percent of the students do not agree with the fact that an ESP program provides with the necessary tools to be able to cope satisfactorily with the different tasks that they will have to face in their future works.

There is no question that students are showing deep interest in what they and their system lacks: an English program that corrects the mistakes and what is missing in the education of future professionals.

Students responded to this question with answers such as “it allows to find a better job because it is not just *English*, but English for a specific purpose in my life.”

QUESTION 5

5) If there were a Specific English program, which area(s) would you choose?

a) Science (Chemistry/biology)

b) Mathematics (Physics and Mathematics)

- c) Art
- d) Humanities (Sociology and Philosophy).
- e) History.

Here the students had the opportunity to choose their area of interest in the event that an ESP program was implemented in their schools. Mathematics – which includes maths and physics—and Humanities –which includes sociology and philosophy—were the two areas with the highest preference (35% respectively). Following the two mentioned areas, it is Arts. With the selections said, it was possible to confirm the students’ inclination.

QUESTION 6

- 6) How many hours of English do you have per week?
- a) 2 hours
 - b) 3 hours
 - c) 4 hours

- d) 5 hours
- e) 6 hours or more

In school C most of the students are taught 2 hours of English per week (92%), which shows why students are dissatisfied. One of the explanations given by the students themselves in question 1 is that the English subject should take more hours per week.

QUESTION 7

- 7) If you had a Specific English program, how many hours of English would you like to have per week?
- a) 2 hours
 - b) 3 hours
 - c) 4 hours
 - d) 5 hours
 - e) 6 hours or more

All the previous analysis can be confirmed with the answer to question number 7 in which students are asked how many hours of English they would rather have in the event that an ESP program functions. Fifty percent of the students chose to double the amount of hours of English they already have in their schools: they would rather have four hours of English for an ESP program.

QUESTION 8

- 9) If you had a Specific English program, do you think you would learn
- e) Much more
 - f) Some more
 - g) A little more
 - h) Very little more

Definitely, students' expectations towards a new teaching methodology reveal that they truly feel dissatisfied with the current methods and that several changes are needed. At this stage, students are able to reflect on their present

experiences with the English subject, thus, saying how much they would benefit from being under ESP training. Students, in this question, made 95% of positive belief towards this new method, which entails serious decision-making and discussion on the current state of EFL in some Chilean schools like school C.

“School D”: Analysis of the questions.

Charts School D: School in the Fifth region, Students’ answers.

QUESTION 1

- 1) Do you think the current situation of English teaching needs a change?
 - a) Yes
 - b) No

In this school, a 74% of the students consider that a change is needed in terms of the present English situation. On the one hand, this reflects that the applicants are dissatisfied with the current ELT in Chile. In order to explain the

participants' disconformity, the following answers are necessary to mention: "The level of English is too basic" 'el nivel es muy básico' or "changing the way English is taught" 'cambio en la forma de explicar.' This reveals that the students are not learning properly due to deficient instruction of this language. On the other hand, a 26% believe that the current ELT situation does not need a change, by interpreting this; it is possible to say that the students are satisfied.

QUESTION 2

2) Do you think English is important for your job in the future?

- a) Very important
- b) Important
- c) Not very important
- d) Doesn't have any importance at all

As it is possible to see, and similarly to the previous schools analyzed, the greatest amount of students agrees and believes that the English they are

taught at school is an important element in their future lives (74%). In the previous analyses for question 2, there was a clear and very strong tendency to believe that English might act as a life-course determiner.

QUESTION 3

3) Would you like the English you learn to be focused on your tertiary or professional/working interests?

a) Yes

b) No

This chart demonstrates that the majority of the participants (84%) would like to learn English focused on their interests in higher education or work, answers such as “it would be useful in tertiary education” as in Spanish ‘Sería útil en la educación superior.’ These answers indicate that students are aware of the fact that English is used in tertiary-level education. In fact, many books and texts are written in English; therefore, students want to learning English focused on their

interests so as to manage jargons and expressions, whereas a 16% do not consider the possibility of learning English focused in their area of interest.

QUESTION 4

4) Do you think an ESP program would give you the necessary tools to achieve a better quality future job?

- a) Yes
- b) No

A great number of the students commented on this question identified by the displayed 74%, claiming that an ESP program would satisfy the needs of the students because it may be more dynamic, and because it focuses on the specific target language 'si es más especializado aprendería más' because 'the lessons would be more dynamic' and 'se enfocaría en las necesidades de cada persona.'

QUESTION 5

5) If there were a Specific English program, which area(s) would you choose?

- a) Science (Chemistry/biology)
- b) Mathematics (Physics and Mathematics)
- c) Art
- d) Humanities (Sociology and Philosophy).
- e) History.

This chart shows that there is a tendency for choosing humanities (Sociology and Philosophy) if there were a Specific English program. However, there are no predominant elections, thus 41% chose humanities (Sociology and Philosophy), 35% chose science (Chemistry and Biology), 18% chose mathematics (Physics and Mathematics), and 6% chose history. In addition to this, this chart

demonstrates the students' inclination towards common subjects imparted in the Chilean schools.

QUESTION 6

- 6) How many hours of English do you have per week?
- a) 2 hours
 - b) 3 hours
 - c) 4 hours
 - d) 5 hours
 - e) 6 hours or more

There is some discrepancy -as it is possible to see in this chart- since there are big, dominant amounts which do not differ greatly. However, it is possible to infer that the students, here, have between 3 (42%) and 6 hours (21%).

QUESTION 7

- 7) If you had a Specific English program, how many hours of English would you like to have per week?
- a) 2 hours
 - b) 3 hours
 - c) 4 hours
 - d) 5 hours
 - e) 6 hours or more

This chart demonstrates that the students do not have a predominant tendency in choosing the amount of hours of Specific English program. The majority (26%) prefers doubling the amount of time spent in their current English classes which is 2 hours (see chart *School D.6*).

QUESTION 8

8) If you had a Specific English program, do you think you would learn

- a) Much more
- b) Some more
- c) A little more
- d) Very little more

It is important to highlight the students' position towards the possible benefits that an ESP program would offer them. Students are aware of the usefulness and importance of being under ESP teaching. This can be seen as 74% of the students think they would learn much more if taught ESP.

“School E”: Analysis of the questions.

Charts School E: School in the Fifth region, Students’ answers.

QUESTION 1

1) Do you think the current situation of English teaching needs a change?

- a) Yes
- b) No

This chart shows that 79% of the applicants do believe that the current ELT in Chile needs a modification, thus being the result of deficient English teaching at their school, thus answers such as “English is too basic” ‘el inglés es muy básico’ denotes that the teaching of this language is far beyond the expected outcomes, in addition, it may be of general knowledge that the current ELT nationwide is lacking good results. On the other hand, there is 21% that consider that the current situation of English does not need any change; in this case, the applicants may feel satisfied or have no idea about the present situation of the teaching of this subject.

QUESTION 2

2) Do you think English is important for your job in the future?

a) Very important

b) Important

c) Not very important

d) Doesn't have any importance at all

The figures in question no. 2 show, once again, that most students are aware of the importance of English for their future careers (55%), and, which will take part in their future professional aspect. In this instance, half of the total of the students surveyed believe English is a very important element for their future.

QUESTION 3

3) Would you like the English you learn to be focused on your tertiary or professional/working interests?

a) Yes

b) No

In this chart the students show a tendency towards the willingness of having English taught on their interests in higher education or work, which totals 70%. This demonstrates that the applicants believe that English must have a purpose in their future lives and a function that would permit them to use this language in a situation in which they are involved. On the contrary, 30% would not consider having English focused on their interests, by this; this result can be interpreted as a satisfaction towards the current ELT in Chile. Moreover, there are students

who claim that General English is an approach that would help them to cope with common communicational situations.

QUESTION 4

4) Do you think an ESP program would give you the necessary tools to achieve a better quality future job?

- a) Yes
- b) No

Only 5% of the students surveyed disagree with the fact an ESP program will allow a better future job. However, it can be inferred that this is because of the little information that students have about ESP. In fact, one answer reflecting this is “For future work, General English is necessary” ‘Para el futuro laboral lo

que importa es ingles general.' Although the previous, the great majority of the students are aware of how important English will be.

QUESTION 5

5) If there were a Specific English program, which area(s) would you choose?

- a) Science (Chemistry/biology)
- b) Mathematics (Physics and Mathematics)
- c) Art
- d) Humanities (Sociology and Philosophy).
- e) History.

This chart demonstrates two predominant tendencies, one tendency shows 42%, which represents Science (Chemistry and Biology). The other tendency, which is 42% as well, represents art. According to this, the results given by this schools reveals that the students have an inclination towards arts, thus giving different results from Chart Question 5 in school D.

QUESTION 6

- 6) How many hours of English do you have per week?
- a) 2 hours
 - b) 3 hours
 - c) 4 hours
 - d) 5 hours
 - e) 6 hours or more

In this school, more than half of the students have 3 hours of English per week (65%). The next big group is the ones that have only 2 hours. If some discrepancy occurs, it might be the result of students' unwillingness or disinterest.

QUESTION 7

- 7) If you had a Specific English program, how many hours of English would you like to have per week?
- a) 2 hours
 - b) 3 hours
 - c) 4 hours
 - d) 5 hours
 - e) 6 hours or more

This chart shows the amount of hours that the students would have if they had a Specific English program. As shown, there is no predominant tendency. The

results were the following: A) Two hours, 35%; B) Three hours, 15%; C) Four hours, 25%; D) Five hours, 35%; and E) Six hours or more, 25%.

QUESTION 8

- 8) If you had a Specific English program, do you think you would learn
- a) Much more
 - b) Some more
 - c) A little more
 - d) Very little more

Similarly to the rest of the schools, the constant continues to be option “a” which says that students (60%) are aware of the fact that being under ESP will allow them to learn much more than the program that they currently have in their schools.

“Teachers: Analysis of the Questions”

QUESTION 1

- 1) Do you think the current situation of English teaching needs a change?
 - a) Yes
 - b) No

This chart demonstrates that all of the surveyed teachers agree that the current English teaching situation needs a change (100%). As a fact, an answer such as “improvement in the implementation of new technologies and teacher training” ‘mejoras en implementación de nuevas tecnologías y capacitación docente’ supports the general disconformity of English teachers of the current ELT situation in Chile. The present underlying methodology used in most of the teaching are also a factor that is under evaluation.

QUESTION 2

2) ¿Are you satisfied with the current state of English teaching in Chile?

- a) Yes
- b) No

According to some of the answers provided by the teachers, it is possible to notice teachers' disappointment towards the current state of ELT in Chile, claiming that "more hours of English are needed" 'faltan más horas de clases.' In general, it can be inferred that teachers also see English as an important element; however, they believe something needs to change.

QUESTION 3

- 3) ¿Would you be willing to take part in a potential modification of the English teaching so that it eventually presents better results?
- a) Yes
 - b) No

Most of the surveyed teachers (75%) are willing to take part of a potential modification of the ELT situation in Chile, thus this indicates that teachers are dissatisfied with the results that the students have achieved, besides this, there are answers reflecting that teachers are not the only responsible stakeholder in developing changes to the present condition of Chilean ELT. “New ideas and good exponents” ‘Se necesitan nuevas ideas y buenos exponentes para una buena modificación’. This answer reveals that teachers are seeking good educational projects that would improve the current ELT in Chile.

QUESTION 4

- 4) ¿What do you think would be the result of an English teaching methodology if this was focused on the student's professional or tertiary needs?
- a) Insufficient
 - b) Regular
 - c) Positive
 - d) No changes

Even though it could be seen teachers' positive attitude towards ESP (75%), they claim that it may not give immediate results. Nonetheless, more than half of the surveyed think that a new methodology would, indeed, give some kind of positive results.

QUESTION 5

5) If a change took place in the English teaching methodology existent today, which factors do you think would need to be modified? Please cross (X) your alternative.

More English-class hours		Teacher training		More classrooms		Change in didactic material	
Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
Teachers' Salary increment		Parking lots		Hygiene Control		Changes in the number of students per class	
Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
More and better technology		More and better meal provision		Scholarships		Teachers' Motivational Workshops	
Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
More and better bibliography		Changes in the timetable / credit hours		Annual fee increments		Teaching Staff increment	
Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No

The chart above is the original, statistical representation shown in the previous page, which gives us a clearer idea of the factors considered. In this chart, all of the teachers surveyed considered the fact of having an increment in English teaching hours. This reflects that the current amount of hours for ELT is not enough in Chile. Teacher training reflects that teachers are lacking tools for improving their lessons, while the increment in the teachers' wages reflects that teacher are dissatisfied with the present salary. Teaching training workshop demonstrates that teachers do need to learn new ways of teaching and have an increase in their motivation.

More and better bibliographic resources shows that the current bibliographic resources existent in Chilean schools are not giving effective results, while increasing teacher staff indicates that the amount of English teachers in Chile is insufficient. Besides, more and better technology shows that most of the lessons

taught in Chile are considered to be old-fashioned, lacking technology and innovative materials to comply with the students learning process.

Half of the teachers surveyed did not consider having more parking lots or an increment in the annual fee.

“Administrative Members: Analysis of the Questions”

QUESTION 1

- 1) Do you think the current situation of English teaching needs a change?
 - a) Yes
 - b) No

All of the surveyed administrators do consider that the current situation of English teaching needs a change. By interpreting the result of this chart it is

possible to infer that there is a general discontent in the current outcome of ELT in Chile.

QUESTION 2

2) ¿Have you heard about English for Specific Purposes (ESP)?

a) Yes

b) No

None of the members surveyed knew about ESP.

QUESTION 3

- 3) ¿Do you see ESP as a tool that can allow Chilean students to have more access to the world of work?
- a) Yes
 - b) No

In this chart an 80% of the applicants believe that ESP is a tool that would help students to have a better access to the work market. They acknowledge that English taught for the students' interest would be an improvement for their future career. Answers such as "the job market is very competitive, knowing another language unbolts opportunities" 'El mercado laboral está muy competitivo, manejar otra lengua abre mayores oportunidades' reflect that English does have an impact in Chilean peoples' life. The opposite result shows that 20% of the applicants believe that ESP is not useful or that students do not have a developed idea of what their objectives are after finishing high-school 'Muchos alumnos no tienen claro qué quieren estudiar una vez egresados del colegio.'

QUESTION 4

4) After knowing how an ESP program would benefit students, would you be willing to incorporate it into your institution's high-school?

a) Yes

b) No

All of the members surveyed showed a positive attitude towards implementing ESP in their institution after knowing how this works and what it would offer students. Members agree with this fact and claim that "they would be better-prepared to face the world of work" 'saldrían major preparados para enfrentar el mundo laboral.'

QUESTION 5

5) If your answer to question no. 4 is “yes,” would you implement ESP

as:

a) elective hours?

b) replacing the General English hours?

This chart demonstrates that a 60% of the participants would implement ESP as elective hours, giving the possibility for the students to choose this special program, whereas 40% would substitute General English for ESP, thus not giving the students the option to have this special program as elective hours.

QUESTION 6

6) If a change took place in the English teaching methodology existent today, which factors do you think would need to be modified? Please cross (X) your alternative.

More English-class hours		Teacher training		More classrooms		Change in didactic material	
Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
Teachers' Salary increment		Parking lots		Hygiene Control		Changes in the number of students per class	
Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
More and better technology		More and better meal provision		Scholarships		Teachers' Motivational Workshops	
Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No
More and better bibliography		Changes in the timetable / credit hours		Annual fee increments		Teaching Staff increment	
Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No	Yes	No

Similarly to the previous one, this chart is the original, statistical information of the factors considered in the previous page, which is now shown in Spanish. According to the members surveyed, not only more English-class hours would be needed if ESP was to be implemented in high-school, but also teacher training, change in didactic material, and more and better technology. Members claim that changes in the amount of students per class are needed, and, therefore, changes in the timetable so that ESP takes place at high-school level.

3.6.1. Findings

As the data from the students' survey has been gathered and further analyzed, it is possible to make conclusions about the general perception that the pupils have in terms of the current ELT situation in Chile and if they believe a change needs to be made that would be beneficial for their professional future lives.

In the next section, an analysis per group of participants will be provided in order to clarify and describe the general context and results of the students (key participants of the learning-teaching process) of all the surveyed schools.

PIE CHART 1 – ANALYSIS

- 1) Do you think the current situation of English teaching needs a change?
 - a) Yes
 - b) No

In this chart it is necessary to say that most of the students do believe that the current ELT situation in Chile needs a change (75%). On the one hand, it is possible to infer by the answers provided by them that the underlying methodology employed by Chilean teachers are not delivering positive results.

On the other hand, students do not believe that the present ELT situation does not need any changes (25%), hence providing positive feedback of their English teaching of their school, but not from the national circumstance.

PIE CHART 2 – ANALYSIS

2) Do you think English is important for your job in the future?

- a) Very important
- b) Important
- c) Not very important
- d) Doesn't have any importance at all

This demonstrates that most of the students do believe that English is important for their future lives (71%) while a (21%) do consider English to be important. In conclusion to this chart it is possible to identify that most of the applicants have a general idea that English is necessary. A (3%) state that is not very important and only a (1%) consider that English is not important at all.

PIE CHART 3 – ANALYSIS

3) Would you like the English you learn to be focused on your tertiary or professional/working interests?

a) Yes

b) No

Most of the students (82%) do consider the possibility of having English taught for their interest in order to comply with their tertiary, professional or working duties in the future. For instance, this demonstrates that the students have acknowledged that English is a language that would be of benefit for the Chileans; hence, it gives more tools for improving their working situation. On the contrary, an (18%) do not consider learning English focused on their tertiary, professional and working situation, thus preferring English for communicational or survival purposes.

PIE CHART 4 – ANALYSIS

4) Do you think an ESP program would give you the necessary tools to achieve a better quality future job?

a) Yes

b) No

Most of the students surveyed (93%) believe that an ESP program would give them the necessary tools to achieve a better quality job in the future, for instance, the students acknowledge that in jobs, it is necessary to use jargons and/or expressions that are common in their job context. On the contrary, only a (7%) believe that ESP would not help them achieve a better job quality.

PIE CHART 5 – ANALYSIS

5) If there were a Specific English program, which area(s) would you choose?

- a) Science (Chemistry/biology)
- b) Mathematics (Physics and Mathematics)
- c) Art
- d) Humanities (Sociology and Philosophy).
- e) History.

The general results displayed in the chart are the following:

1. A (35%) would have humanities (Sociology and Philosophy).
2. A (22%) would have art.
3. A (19%) would have mathematics (Physics and Mathematics).
4. A (19%) would have science (Chemistry/biology).
5. A (5%) would have history.

The results are multiple, so as a conclusion, ESP would be applicable in the most common subjects imparted in the Chilean education.

PIE CHART 6 – ANALYSIS

- 6) How many hours of English do you have per week?
- a) 2 hours
 - b) 3 hours
 - c) 4 hours
 - d) 5 hours
 - e) 6 hours or more

The results in this chart are multiple, thus indicating a tendency for the option B (35%), which is 4 hours. The next option with the highest percentage is A) 2 hours (33%) while the other two options are E) 6 hours or more (9%), and D) 5 hours (5%).

PIE CHART 7 – ANALYSIS

7) If you had a Specific English program, how many hours of English would you like to have per week?

- a) 2 hours
- b) 3 hours
- c) 4 hours
- d) 5 hours

Most of the students surveyed chose option C (34%). The other results are the following (from the highest percentage to the lowest):

Option D: 19%

Option E: 19%

Option A: 15%

Option B: 13%

PIE CHART 8 – ANALYSIS

- 8) If you had a Specific English program, do you think you would learn
- a) Much more
 - b) Some more
 - c) A little more
 - d) Very little more

This chart indicates how much the participants would learn if they had a Specific English program.

The results were the following:

- a) Much more (76%)
- b) Some more (17%)
- c) A little more (5%)
- d) Very little more (2%)

The high expectancy may be related to the fact that students are not satisfied with the current English learning and teaching. Thus needing and desiring a new type of methodology in order to fulfill their needs and interests.

4. CONCLUSIONS

It was the aim of the current study to present ESP (English for Specific Purposes) as an alternative to improve the current levels of English archived in the public school system and whether the Chilean educational system meets the necessary requirements to implement ESP programs in the high school system.

The percentages assumed through the working hypotheses (p 49) were highly met, since stakeholders demonstrated a high disappointment towards ELT in Chile conveying that, even though it takes some hours (in some cases several) from their schedules, it is not purposeful and/or not in line with their needs and expectations. Also, it was demonstrated that stakeholders see an innovative method as a possible solution to the many deficiencies that ELT has in the country, which is ESP.

As reviewed in the literature, the speaking of English of a country carries along economic boost and other positive implications; the stakeholders surveyed showed an awareness that their knowledge of English would not only mean a possible economic improvement for them, but for the country as well. This is in line with the statements found in the document Índice del Nivel de Inglés (EF EPI, PDF file) and as displayed earlier in the research, 9 out 10 ESL countries are developed.

Another important aspect deeply studied was ELT in Chile regarding the different conditions, different contexts and places, and the way in which it is implemented in the different areas of society. Stakeholders provided the necessary information to achieve the conclusion. Regarding the latter, it is possible to conclude that a high percentage (over 80%) of the students, teachers and administrative are not satisfied with the methodologies currently being employed in the teaching of English in Chile, claiming that improvements and modifications must take place for improvement. ESP is proposed as a solution; however it was used as an excuse to convey that General English is not enough to satisfy the learners' needs and that any new teaching method that may mean improvements is going to be welcome into a failing system such as the Chilean, for instance less than 20% were satisfied with the current status of ELT in Chile.

It is of great importance to point out that one of our findings on the literature review is that ESP programs do not need a high level of English as a basis, from which to support itself; the level of these courses starts at an elementary level as any other General English course, and they develop into more advanced levels throughout their duration. Kitkauskienė (1) says that there are different levels of English, acknowledging the fact that teaching English is always based on the language skills acquired at a secondary school; one must understand the need to make language a professionally-oriented subject because it should help to

build students' better-professional skills as well as to contribute to their education as active members of society. The fact that secondary students could learn English for Specific Purposes is something possible considering the knowledge teachers have of a need to change the status quo of ELT in Chile today, their willingness to participate in the change, and their dissatisfaction of students' outcome with the present methodology.

It is important to mention that one of our limitations was not having the necessary resources to perform this study: to revise literature and any source of information that could provide useful information to help link realities and theory which support the current investigation. Some more limitations were time, since in order to find deeper quality information it is necessary to have a longer period of time and also a larger team in order to delegate more tasks and reach further goals. Nevertheless, given the time provided and people implied in the present work, important findings, especially through the surveys were reached on the perception towards ELT granted by the very protagonists of education, allowing the present work to have a rather objective prism. It is also important to say that such investigation has an innovative connotation since little or no research had been done regarding this topic until now in Chile.

The main findings were not only of tangible characteristics, but also of the processes that are endured at a psychological level by the different stakeholders in the educational process. Consequently, Krashen states that the need of

students to find themselves within a second language environment in order to “pick up” a given language at conscious or subconscious level is a manifested necessity shown through the many surveys conducted and the comments the students provided.

It may be concluded that in order to apply and eventually incorporate ESP into a given educational system, not many changes are really needed; therefore, no significant investment, infrastructural modifications, among others must take place. Notwithstanding, changes in the syllabi, teachers’ training and the need of proper pedagogy certification are, undoubtedly the most difficult challenges to be faced at a possible ESP incorporation. This is at least what may be drawn as a conclusion from the stakeholders’ opinions and the literature reviewed. Besides the previous, it will be necessary to conduct further studies to determine financial and economical assets and to approach the official entities to have such a specific program like ESP working in a given school.

As proposed by Krashen (19) and in line with the principle of *meaningful input*, another important aspect to be considered was the interest from the students to receive such instruction, subject that was proven to be positive during the study; however, deeper study and a bigger sample would be needed in order to reach further conclusions.

Based on the economical, managing, infrastructural, governmental and instructional aspects that were diligently studied it was possible to determine

that the Chilean education has most of the necessary conditions to have a much better level of ELT than the one it currently has, and its inefficiency lies on Chile's cultural and social flaws that make difficult and inadequate the correct functioning of English learning-teaching process. In addition, authorities seem to be interested in getting results; therefore, they might be willing to invest in the implementation of ESP as an alternative and experimental method.

According to the literature studied, ESP is a full, effective and responsible method that will, in fact, aid the learning of English. It has been proven throughout the literature study that it can be applied in any context, at any age and even at school level. Nevertheless, the lack of concrete ESP applications and results in Chile raises the questioning whether it would be useful and fruitful or not, hence, the need for further study seeking the possibility of direct implementation to students in the average school situation in Chile.

Through this work, the ground bases of Chilean education and what it conveys were outlined in regards to the possibility of incorporating not only ESP, but any teaching method that comes in aid of the weak ELT in Chile. Researchers, teachers, investigators or stakeholders who might wish to introduce an innovating methodology other than the General English that is implemented in Chile, will find a meaningful source of information in the present study in order to learn about the various elements at play and their context, and to have an objective, well informed view of the *zeitgeist* witnessed in our system. The

quantitative as well as the qualitative data has been analyzed as objectively as possible, retrieved from the core of our education reality, from the people who keep it on the move: the stakeholders and mainly the future professionals.

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Appendix II School B Students' Mood

Answered questions	Qualitative data
Students average	
12	100,0%
12	100,0%
12	100,0%
12	100,0%
11	91,7%
12	100,0%
12	100,0%
12	100,0%
11	91,7%
12	100,0%
11	91,7%
12	100,0%
9	75,0%
12	100,0%
12	100,0%
12	100,0%
9	75,0%
12	100,0%
10	83,3%
12	100,0%
11	91,7%
11	91,7%
12	100,0%
12	100,0%
9	75,0%
11	91,7%
12	100,0%
11	91,7%
12	100,0%
9	75,0%
10	83,3%
12	100,0%
9	75,0%
12	100,0%
11	91,7%

	11	91,7%
	12	100,0%
	12	100,0%
	12	100,0%
	12	100,0%
	12	100,0%
	12	100,0%
	12	100,0%
Average		94,3%

Appendix IV School D Students' Mood

Answered questions	Qualitative data
Students average	
12	100%
12	100%
12	100%
8	67%
10	83%
12	100%
7	58%
12	100%
9	75%
9	75%
12	100%
10	83%
12	100%
9	75%
11	92%
8	67%
9	75%
12	100%
8	67%
Average	85%

Appendix V: School E Students' Mood

Answered questions	Qualitative data
	Students average
11	92%
10	83%
10	83%
12	100%
12	100%
11	92%
12	100%
12	100%
12	100%
12	100%
9	75%
12	100%
8	67%
12	100%
9	75%
12	100%
8	67%
10	83%
12	100%
11	92%
Average	90%

Appendix VI: School E Students' Survey

SCHOOL: A																																
PART.	QUESTION 1				QUESTION 2				QUESTION 3				QUESTION 4				QUESTION 5			QUESTION 6			QUESTION 7			QUESTION 8						
	a	b	Comment		a	b	c	d	a	b	c	d	a	b	c	d	a	b	c	d	e	a	b	c	d	e	a	b	c	d	Comment	
1	x		el inglés es bueno, estudiando se aprende.																												existe la base, pero ayudaría.	
2	x		el inglés es bueno		x																										sería más interesante porque estaría enfocado en intereses particulares.	
3	x		el inglés es bueno		x																										Me ayudaría en lo que estudiaría.	
4	x		avanza más en calidad		x																										aprendería más	
5	x		el inglés es bueno		x																										porque sería más interesante.	
6	x		el inglés es bueno																												sería más interesante porque estaría enfocado en intereses particulares.	
7	x		el inglés es bueno																												no de importancia personal	
8	x		el inglés es bueno																												aprendería un poco más	
9	x		debería mejorar		x																										Obtendría más herramientas	
10	x		el inglés es bueno		x																										Obtendría más herramientas	
12	x		presenta satisfacción con el nivel de su establecimiento																												Es necesario el interés propio primero que todo	
13	x		presenta satisfacción con el nivel de su establecimiento		x																										Más horas de inglés, mayor conocimiento y aprendizaje	
14	x		refleja necesidad de mayor uso de TICs y clases didáctica		x																										El inglés es un idioma muy complejo	
15	x		presenta satisfacción con el nivel de su establecimiento		x																										Mantiene interés por inglés general con fragmentos de especialización	
16	x		presenta satisfacción con el nivel de su establecimiento		x																										cree que sería útil para combatir la dificultad de aprender inglés	
17	x		presenta satisfacción con el nivel de su establecimiento		x																										Más contenidos basados en interés y menos distracciones	
18	x		presenta satisfacción con el nivel de su establecimiento		x																										Ayudaría en el futuro laboral	
19	x		demuestra conformidad pero podría ser mejor		x																										Manifiesta interés por especialización ya que de otra forma es muy básico	
20	x		demuestra poca claridad																												Reitera su 0 interés	
21	x		presenta satisfacción con el nivel de su establecimiento		x																										Es necesario el interés propio primero que todo	
22	x		La ejercitación de la producción oral necesita mejorar.		x																										Entrega contenido y herramientas realmente necesarias.	
23	x				x																										Porque estaría basado en contenido ya estudiado.	
24	x		Está bien tal cual es.		x																										Más especializado y más divertido.	
25	x		Está bien tal cual es.		x																										Ya que hay mayor práctica del idioma.	
26	x				x																										Ya que me especializaría en mi área de interés.	
27	x		Está bien tal cual es.		x																										Mucho más.	
28	x		Está bien tal cual está. Nosotros como alumnos debemos dedicarle más tiempo y atención.		x																											Es importante aprender aspectos de distinta índole como fonética.
29	x		Se deberían implementar separación por niveles.		x																										Estaríamos más motivados debido a las herramientas realmente necesarias.	
30	x		Porque deberían ser más dinámicas para incentivar a los alumnos.		x																										Ya que me especializaría en mi área de interés.	
31	x		Porque deberían ser más dinámicas para incentivar a los alumnos.		x																										No me gusta inglés.	

Appendix VIII: School C Students' Survey

School C																													
QUESTION 1		QUESTION 2				QUESTION 3				QUESTION 4				QUESTION 5				QUESTION 6				QUESTION 7				QUESTION 8			
a	b	a	b	c	d	a	b	c	d	a	b	c	d	a	b	c	d	e	a	b	c	d	e	a	b	c	d	Comment	
x			x		x					x				x					x									Mucho más.	
	Porque no se enseña lo necesario para poder expresarse en inglés.	x																										Poco interés.	
x	Porque no hay interés por el idioma.	x																										Entrega contenido y herramientas realmente necesarias.	
x	Porque son necesarias más horas de inglés.	x																										En el liceo se enseña lo básico.	
x	Porque lo estudiado en el liceo no me sirve realmente.	x																										Se entregarían herramientas nuevas.	
x	Está bien tal cual está.		x		x																							Sería más claro para entender.	
x	Porque el contenido es muy básico.	x																										Me entregaría herramientas que no se entregaron en el colegio.	
x	Porque para aprender más se necesitan más factores.	x																										El aprendizaje será mayor porque habrá menos personas en la sala.	
x	Porque deberían ser más dinámicas para incentivar a los alumnos.	x																										Ya que hay mayor práctica del idioma.	
x	Porque deberían ser más dinámicas para incentivar a los alumnos.	x																										Estaríamos más motivados debido a las herramientas realmente necesarias.	
x	Porque deberían ser más dinámicas para incentivar a los alumnos.	x																										En el liceo se enseña lo básico.	
x	Está bien tal cual está.	x																										-	
x	-	x																										Estaríamos más motivados debido a las herramientas realmente necesarias.	
x	Porque casi ni se utiliza y además son muy pocas horas de inglés.	x																										Aprendería mejor el idioma al dedicarle más tiempo.	
x	Docentes mal preparados.	x																										Permite expandir nuestro vocabulary y lograr fluidez.	
x	Porque el contenido es muy básico, incompleto, e inconcluso.	x																										-	
x	-	x																										Porque hoy en día es muy necesario.	
x	Porque el contenido es muy básico.	x																										-	
x	Porque no aprendemos sobre el tema.	x																										Porque es una herramienta necesaria en un nuevo trabajo.	
x	Porque no enseñan un inglés comunicacional.	x																										Más especializado y más divertido.	
x	Porque no es completo.	x																										Ya que no tuve inglés en la enseñanza básica.	
x	-	x																										En mi colegio lo hacen bien.	
x	Porque el contenido es muy básico.	x																										En el liceo se enseña lo básico.	
x	Porque el contenido es muy básico.	x																										Porque la enseñanza sería mejor.	
x	Debería ser generalizado y equitativamente.	x																										Mucho, siempre y cuando me interese.	
x	Docentes mal preparados.	x																										Porque si no quiero aprender, no aprendo.	
x	La educación es de mala calidad.	x																										Ya que me especializaría en mi área de interés.	
x	Porque no es completo.	x																										Ya que me especializaría en mi área de interés.	
x	Porque no se enseña lo necesario para poder expresarse en inglés.	x																										Entrega contenido y herramientas realmente necesarias.	
x	Nuestro colegio nos enseña un inglés adecuado: básico.	x																										Porque estaría basado en contenido ya estudiado.	
x	La educación es de mala calidad.	x																										Porque me permite dominar más el idioma.	
x	Porque son necesarias más horas de inglés.	x																										Porque mayor cantidad de horas semanales significa mayor aprendizaje.	
x	Porque el contenido es muy básico.	x																										-	
x	Porque los estudiantes no aprenden sólo con guías.	x																										Estaríamos más motivados debido a las herramientas realmente necesarias.	
x	Porque no es completo.	x																										Mayor aprendizaje debido a la relevancia de los contenidos.	
x	Está bien tal cual está. Nosotros como alumnos debemos dedicarle más tiempo y atención.	x																										-	
x	Porque el contenido es muy básico.	x																										Porque hoy en día es muy necesario.	
x	Inglés básico y fome	x																										habría más concentración mejor calidad	
x	Sería mejor un cambio	x																										Aprendería más porque le interesaría	
x	Inglés básico	x																										sería especializado por ende se aprendería más	
x	No aprenden	x																										más horas = mejora del inglés	
x	No aprenden	x																										sería mejor para el aprendizaje	

Appendix X: School E Students' Survey

School E																																		
QUESTION 1		QUESTION 2				QUESTION 3				QUESTION 4				QUESTION 5				QUESTION 6				QUESTION 7				QUESTION 8								
a	b	Comment	a	b	c	d	a	b	Comment	a	b	Comment	a	b	c	d	e	a	b	c	d	e	a	b	c	d	e	a	b	c	d	Comment		
x		No necesita cambios. Está super bien.	x				x		Pondría más interés por el tema enfocado.	x								x													x	Reforzaría el estudio.		
x		Porque a mí me cuesta y para mí está bien.					x	x	Porque yo no necesito inglés; no me deberían enseñar.									x												x	Porque no me gusta y no me interesa.			
x		Creo que la enseñanza es buena.	x				x			x		Aprenderíamos mucho más.						x																
x		Necesita cambios ya que lo que uno vé es solo lo básico.					x		Porque hoy en día, en casi todas las carreras es importante tener una base.	x		Igual esto va dependiendo en el ámbito que lo ocupe.						x															Ya que habría una visión en la cual podemos expresarnos de distinta manera.	
x		No existe respeto hacia el profesor, el mismo deja que los alumnos hagan lo que quieran en las clases. En las clases no tiene autoridad.	x				x		Ya que así habría mayor motivación de parte del alumno.	x		Ya que si se tiene más tiempo mucho mejor.	x																				Ya que se podría indagar mucho más en los temas de interés y en los que los alumnos están menos capacitados.	
x		Bien hasta ahora					x			x		Pero igual no lo tomaría.						x															Porque no pondría mucha dedicación.	
x		acusar necesidad de hablar el inglés y de cambio de ritmo anual	x						demuestra interés por el inglés cotidiano	x		Para futuro laboral importa el inglés en general						x															las clases serían más fluidas y se aprendería mucho más	
x		Faltan horas de inglés					x		pondría más atención e interés en las clases	x		Laboralmente es mejor pagada una persona que habla inglés						x															se enseñarían cosas más específicas	
x		más horas de inglés	x						demuestra interés por el inglés cotidiano	x		ayudaría mucho						x															demuestra más enseñanza	
x		debería ser más didáctico, más pronunciación y menos gramático	x						demuestra interés por el inglés cotidiano	x		permite mejor futuro laboral y mejor base de inglés						x															tendría una buena base y aprendería mucho más inglés	
x		acusar abuso en uso de libro					x			x																							demuestra nulo interés por la asignatura	
x		se debería saber hablando inglés del colegio	x						es necesario para hablar con extranjeros	x		requiere aprender de otras fuentes ya que no alcanza con la enseñanza escolar de hoy						x															aumento en dedicación dado el interés personal	
x							x			x								x																
x		Los alumnos no manejan lo básico					x		Ayudaría en los intereses personales	x		porque se aprendería más						x															me gustaría aprender más	
x		Sí porque es la lengua con la que se habla mundialmente	x							x								x																
x		Cambio en la forma de explicar	x						para aprender más	x		Sí, para el trabajo						x																Si aprendería más
x							x			x								x																
		No sabe					x		Porque sí	x		dependiendo lo que uno quiere estudiar																						
x		El nivel del país es muy básico	x						es un método de encontrar trabajo	x		te enseñaría cosas necesarias	x					x																Acusa flojera de los estudiantes
x		Tiene reforzar más lo básico					x		creo que en la mayoría de los trabajos piden un mínimo de inglés	x								x															demuestra interes por la asignatura.	

SAMPLE SURVEY

Administrative Members

Encuesta para Administrativos

Esta encuesta se realiza para recopilar información acerca de la opinión de los docentes sobre la metodología usada en la asignatura de inglés y una posible modificación en su implementación a través de la aplicación de una metodología que apunte a satisfacer las necesidades e intereses de los alumnos de tercer y cuarto año medio.

Mediante la aplicación de programas ESP, los cuales están enfocados en el uso específico del lenguaje en una determinada área de estudio, se aspira a satisfacer los aspectos mencionados previamente, haciendo del inglés una herramienta útil para enfrentar el mundo laboral y académico.

1. ¿Cree usted que el inglés que se imparte en el sistema educativo chileno necesita un cambio?

- a) Sí.
- b) No.

Explique Sí, Considero que debería atender a la diversas necesidades educativas referidas por ejemplo a los campos de acción de los estudiantes como en el caso de los liceos TP Técnico Profesionales, generando un plus a sus desempeños.

Por otra parte, debe hacerse un cambio significativo puesto que desde el primer año básico se enseña inglés.... ¿Cuanto los estudiantes aprenden y llegan a aplicar?. Ciertamente en colegios privados o subvencionados los resultados son mucho mas favorables debido a que en sus mallas curriculares existe mayor cantidad de horas destinadas a esta área en específico.

2. ¿Ha escuchado hablar acerca de los programas de inglés con Fines Específicos (ESP)?

- a) Sí.
- b) No.

Explique NO _____

3. ¿Ve usted ESP como una herramienta que puede significar un mayor acceso al mundo laboral de los alumnos chilenos?

- a) Sí.
- b) No.

Explique, Permite responder satisfactoriamente a las necesidades y hacer una educación más pertinente, pues no todos los estudiantes están capacitados para el idioma o sacarán provecho de él debido a sus realidades socioculturales, siendo siempre significativo su aprendizaje. _____

4. ¿Al conocer cómo un programa ESP beneficia a los alumnos estaría dispuesto a implementarlo en la enseñanza media de su establecimiento?

- a) Sí.
b) No.

Explique. Es posible aunque ello no depende solo del establecimiento puesto que hay administraciones superiores y planes y programas establecidos Ministerialmente, para el caso de los liceos Municipales o Corporativizados de administración delegada.

5. Si su respuesta al ítem no. 5 es "Sí", lo impartiría como

- a) Horas electivas
b) En reemplazo de las horas de inglés general.

Explique _____

6. De llevarse a cabo un cambio en el método de enseñanza en inglés, ¿qué factores y/o condiciones cree usted deberían modificarse? Sírvase marcar su alternativa con una **X**.

Si cree que no es importante **NO** marque el ítem.

Aumento en las horas de inglés		Capacitación Necesaria		Aumento de salas y espacios		Cambio o aumento recursos didácticos	
Sí	No	Sí	No	Sí	No	Sí	No
X		X			X	X	

Aumento de sueldos de profesores		Estacionamientos		Mejoras de medidas sanitarias		Cambios en la cantidad de alumnos por curso	
Sí	No	Sí	No	Sí	No	Sí	No
	X		X		X	X	

Mayor y mejor tecnología		Más y mejor alimentación		Necesidad de becas		Talleres de motivación docente	
Sí	No	Sí	No	Sí	No	Sí	No
X		X		X			X

Mayor y mejor recurso bibliográfico		Cambios en la carga horaria		Aumento de aranceles		Aumento de personal docente	
Sí	No	Sí	No	Sí	No	Sí	No
X		X			X		X

Muchas gracias por su tiempo y cooperación.

OK Suerte y ánimo para su proyecto.

SAMPLE SURVEY

Students

nº 20 L69V

Encuesta Alumnos

Esta encuesta se realiza para recopilar información acerca de la opinión de los estudiantes sobre la asignatura de inglés. **Sírvase marcar la alternativa con una X**

1) ¿Crees que el estado actual de la enseñanza del inglés necesita algún cambio?

a) Sí
 b) No

Explique:
que pueda ser más completo.

2) ¿Crees que hablar inglés es importante para tu trabajo en el futuro?

A) Muy importante
 B) Importante
 C) No tan importante
 D) Sin ninguna importancia

3) ¿Le gustaría que el inglés que aprende estuviese enfocado en sus intereses de educación superior/profesionales o laborales?

a) Sí
 b) No

Explique:
NO NOS COSTARÍA TANTO PARA COMUNICARNOS CON EXTRANJEROS QUE SEPAN DE INGLÉS.

4) ¿Crees que un programa de inglés especializado te entregaría las herramientas necesarias para poder optar por un futuro laboral de mejor calidad?

a) Sí
 b) No

Explique:
PARA ESTAR MUCHO MÁS PREPARADO.

5) ¿Si existiese un programa de inglés especializado qué área(s) seleccionarías?

a) Ciencias (química/biología)
 b) Matemáticas (física y matemáticas).
 c) Artes.
 d) Humanista (sociología y filosofía).

Encuesta Alumnos

- e) Historia.
- 6) ¿Cuántas horas de inglés tienes a la semana?
 - a) 2 horas.
 - b) 3 horas.
 - c) 4 horas.
 - d) 5 horas.
 - e) 6 horas o más.

b) No
Explique:

- 7) ¿Si estuvieses en un programa de inglés especializado cuántas horas de inglés te gustaría tener a la semana?
 - a) 2 horas.
 - b) 3 horas.
 - c) 4 horas.
 - d) 5 horas.
 - e) 6 horas o más.

c) No tan importante

- 8) Si usted estuviera en un programa de inglés especializado crees que aprenderías:
 - a) Mucho más
 - b) Algo más
 - c) Poco más
 - d) Muy poco más

Explique:
En la Básica no tube Asignatura de ingles
por lo tanto no entiendo mucho, pero me gustaria
Aprender un poco más de Ingles.

- 9) ¿Crees que un programa de inglés especializado te entregaría las herramientas para mejorar tu nivel de inglés?
 - a) Sí
 - b) No

Explique:

Para saber mucho más acerca de

- 10) Si existiese un programa de inglés especializado qué área(s) preferirías?
 - a) Ciencias (química/biología)
 - b) Matemáticas (física y matemáticas)
 - c) Artes
 - d) Humanidades (sociología y filosofía)

